

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Common Framework Defining the Methodology for Achieving User-Centred Quality Objectives

DELIVERABLE 6.1

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Abstract

This document presents a user-centred design framework aligned with OPERAS' openness, diversity, and inclusion values. It empowers users and involves them in decision-making processes for service creation, serving as a valuable resource to enhance user engagement and foster a user-centric approach within the OPERAS community. Part A introduces foundational concepts, principles and processes for user-centred design and research in OPERAS projects. Part B lists methods and tools derived from literature and existing projects, benefiting user researchers and people who do research (PWDR). The framework will continuously be refined and updated for relevance and effectiveness throughout the project.

Contents

Abbreviations	6
Executive summary	7
List of figures	9
List of tables	9
1. Introduction	10
1.1 <i>Introducing the UCQ-FRAME</i>	13
1.2 <i>UX and UCD in the context of OPERAS-PLUS</i>	14
1.3 <i>Benefits of the UCQ-FRAME</i>	17
1.4 <i>Relationships with other OPERAS-PLUS work packages and deliverables</i>	19
1.5 <i>How to use the UCQ-FRAME</i>	20
Part A – Common Framework Defining the Methodology for Achieving User-Centred Quality Objectives	23
2. UCD principles and UX process cycle	23
2.1 <i>Foundational concepts related to the UCD process</i>	25
2.2 <i>Guiding UCD principles</i>	30
2.3 <i>UCD process cycle</i>	33
2.3.1 <i>ResearchOps: supporting and operationalising the UCD process</i>	36
3. <i>Planning a UCD project</i>	50
4. User research: context of use and user requirements	57
4.1 <i>Types of user research</i>	57
4.2 <i>Context of use</i>	60
4.3 <i>User requirements</i>	68
5. Design solutions	70
5.1 <i>Principles for UI design</i>	71
5.2 <i>UI prototyping</i>	71
5.3 <i>UI guidelines</i>	75
6. Evaluating the design	76
6.1 <i>Usability tests</i>	77

6.2 Usability inspections.....	79
6.3 User surveys and standardised questionnaires.....	80
6.4 Long-term monitoring.....	82
7. Conclusions and next steps	83
Part B: Methods and tools for UCD.....	85
8. References	115

Abbreviations

AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (legal status under Belgian law for international non-profit associations)
AoC	Assembly of Commons
EA	Executive Assembly
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
HCD	Human-Centred Design
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OS	Open Science
PD	Participatory Design
PWDR	People Who Do Research
ResearchOps	Research Operations (community)
RI	Research Infrastructure
SAC	Scientific Advisory Committee
SIG	Special Interest Groups
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
STB	Services and Technology Board
UCD	User-Centred Design
UCQ-FRAME	OPERAS-PLUS D6.1: Common Framework Defining the Methodology for Achieving User-Centred Quality Objectives
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
TBD	To Be Determined
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The OPERAS-PLUS project brings together 16 partners from 11 countries, including 13 beneficiaries, 2 associated partners, and 1 affiliated partner. Its primary objective is to address challenges hindering the progress of OPERAS in becoming an operational ERIC by 2028. The project focuses on two pillars: infrastructure establishment and the development of OPERAS services, particularly the construction of its catalogue.

Within the Services Management pillar, WP6 – User Engagement and Training, is dedicated to achieving several objectives. This includes identifying and describing existing OPERAS services and their target user groups, developing a user-centred methodological framework, implementing the framework in specific services, and creating a training framework for open science and scholarly communication to enhance user engagement. The work package adopts a user-centred design (UCD) approach to address user needs and gather feedback effectively, enabling project teams to improve the user experience and engagement with OPERAS services.

Deliverable 6.1, part of WP6 – User Engagement and Training, introduces the UCQ-FRAME as a methodological framework for achieving successful user-centred projects. The UCQ-FRAME supports UX research and user-centred design by providing processes, methods/tools, and practices. The UCQ-FRAME aligns with OPERAS' values of open scholarly communication, diversity and inclusion. It empowers users and involves them in decision-making processes for service creation. This framework is a valuable resource for OPERAS project teams seeking to adopt user-centred approaches and enhance user engagement in open scholarly communication and publishing.

In Part A of the framework, foundational concepts, principles, and methods are introduced to guide user-centred design processes and integrate user experience research and design in projects. The framework outlines an iterative design cycle with tailored methods and tools, following the ISO 9241 series of standards and incorporating the research operations framework described in section 2.3.1. This integration establishes standardised processes and enables systematic evaluation of user experience maturity. In addition to other important considerations, the detailed description of the design cycle emphasises the need for dedicated UX teams, data collection spaces, inclusive participant recruitment, and conducting comprehensive research on the context of use and user requirements. The process progresses through the design phase, aligned with user-system interaction principles, and concludes with the evaluation phase involving feedback collection and enhancements. Following the guidance in Part A, OPERAS will enhance user-centred design practices, foster innovation, and improve the overall user experience.

Part B of the framework presents a list of methods and tools derived from relevant literature, and existing OPERAS projects and services (e.g., GoTriple or Vera). A title, short description, usage guidance, components, key concepts, and additional sources for

further exploration accompany each method. While this deliverable provides a limited overview of each method, a more comprehensive version will be developed within the OPERAS methods bank on the Confluence platform. Researchers are advised to familiarise themselves with the methods and have the flexibility to adapt them to their specific requirements. By leveraging this extensive collection of methods and tools, OPERAS project teams can enhance their user-centred design practices, ensuring the delivery of high-quality user experiences and driving advancements in open scholarly communication within social sciences and humanities.

The UCQ-FRAME, a dynamic and evolving document, will be continuously refined and updated in alignment with the ongoing OPERAS-PLUS project. As a living framework, it reflects the project's iterative nature and commitment to adapt and improve. The UCQ-FRAME (1.0) will undergo iterative revision to meet the project milestone MS6 – First-draft of the methodological framework for achieving user-centred quality objectives of OPERAS services in month 14, and experimentation on different services during the implementation phase in WP6 Task 6.3, ensuring its relevance and effectiveness throughout the project's lifespan.

List of figures

Figure 1. OPERAS-PLUS PERT chart	11
Figure 2: Desirability, feasibility, and viability: the sweet spot for innovation	18
Figure 3: Double Diamond (Adapted from Design Council. Licensed under CC BY 4.0.) 21	
Figure 4: Peter Morville’s User Experience Honeycomb (with minor modification by Katerina Karagianni, 2018).....	24
Figure 5: Integrated evaluation framework of usability and UX (H. Miki 2014).....	29
Figure 6: The UCD process and activities according to ISO 9231-210 standard (modified)	34
Figure 7: Basic UCD process.....	36
Figure 8: ResearchOps map. Source: Kate Towsey	37
Figure 9: Adapted eight pillars of ResearchOps. Source: Emma Boulton	38
Figure 10: Example of UX research canvas. Source: Claudia Masca ((https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVM_nC_Vk=/)	52
Figure 11: Landscape of user research methods. Source: Christian Rohrer (https://www.nngroup.com/articles/which-ux-research-methods/)	58
Figure 12: Example empathy map. Source: https://www.nngroup.com/articles/empathy-mapping/	60
Figure 13: Example of a non-academic persona created for the GoTriple platform. Source: Dumouchel et al. 2020.....	64
Figure 14: Example of a non-academic scenario for the GoTriple platform. Source: Dumouchel et al. 2020.....	65
Figure 15: Example user journey map. Source: Wikimedia	67
Figure 16: Example story map from the OPERAS Vera project. Source: William J. Costello	67
Figure 17: Example wireframe from the OPERAS Vera project. Source: William J. Costello	73
Figure 18: Example of a card sorting session. Source: Yandle (https://www.flickr.com/photos/yandle/907929818/sizes/l/in/photostream/)	74
Figure 19: Example user interface style guide by Material. Source: https://m2.material.io	76

List of tables

Table 1. OPERAS services	12
Table 2: Six UCD principles (ISO 9241-210 2019)	30
Table 3: OPERAS service design and development lifecycle.....	35
Table 4: UX maturity levels to the eight ResearchOps pillars. Source: Pistoia Alliance	42
Table 5: Example of a user need and corresponding user requirement.....	69
Table 6: The methods matrix aligns different methods with the UCD process	86

1. Introduction

The OPERAS-PLUS project consists of 16 partners, comprising 13 beneficiaries, 2 associated and 1 affiliated partner, representing 11 European countries. These partners will support OPERAS as it progresses towards its goal of becoming operational as an ERIC by 2028. The project seeks to empower OPERAS by a) enhancing its governance structure regarding financial, legal, and human resources, b) supporting the network of national nodes and their activities, c) expanding the services portfolio with necessary technology and a monitoring system for service development, and d) broadening OPERAS' impact within the European Research Area (ERA) and globally by welcoming new members and countries to the infrastructure. The ongoing efforts of OPERAS-PLUS are an extension of the results achieved in previous projects (OPERAS-D, OPERAS-P, HIRMEOS, TRIPLE) and will be complemented by valuable insights from ongoing projects (such as COESO, DIAMAS, PALOMERA).

The OPERAS-PLUS project is organised around two pillars: 1) establishing the infrastructure by supporting the legal entity and 2) supporting the development of OPERAS services, particularly the construction of its catalogue (Figure 1). The WP6 - User Engagement and Training, part of Pillar 2: Services Management, has the following objectives:

- Identify and describe the relevant existing OPERAS services and their targeted user groups.
- Develop a shared methodological framework that aims to achieve user-centred quality objectives for OPERAS services.
- Implement the developed framework on specific services to ensure practical application.
- Create an open science and scholarly communication training framework to enhance user engagement with the current OPERAS services.

Figure 1. OPERAS-PLUS PERT chart

OPERAS is committed to developing a comprehensive ecosystem of scholarly communication services that support the whole lifecycle of research and cater to the specific needs of the SSH research community at both local and European levels. Each service is designed to consolidate, aggregate, or federate existing resources across Europe, providing researchers with a single access point to a wide range of resources. Table 1 presents the current OPERAS Service portfolio, which encompasses a range of 13 services. These services are classified into three types and span across different categories, stages of development and user groups. Currently, OPERAS provides three types of services:

- **Managed Services:** These services are available for ordering directly through OPERAS, and OPERAS assumes complete responsibility for their delivery (e.g., GoTriple).
- **Community Services:** These services can only be discovered on the OPERAS website and are managed directly by the respective community provider (e.g., PRISM).
- **Internal Services:** These services, while not available for independent ordering, are essential for the management and operation of the OPERAS federation. They cater to the internal infrastructure needs of OPERAS (e.g. AAI - Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure).“

Table 1. OPERAS services

Service	Status	Type	Category	User groups
GoTriple	Production	Managed	Discovery	SSH researchers; Authors; Editors, Editorial managers; Publishers; Libraries; Translators
PRISM	Production	Community	Quality Assurance	SSH researchers; Authors; Publishers; Libraries
Hypotheses	Production	Community	Research4Society	SSH researchers; Authors; Publishers; Libraries
FitSM Training	Production	Internal	Training	OPERAS members
Metrics	Beta	Managed	Analytics	SSH researchers; Publishers; Libraries
VERA	Beta	Managed	Research4Society	SSH researchers; Publishers; Libraries
OPERAS ID (AAI)	Beta	Internal	Operations	OPERAS members
Messaging	Beta	Internal	Operations	OPERAS members
Pathfinder	Alpha	Managed	Discovery	Authors; Publishers; Editors, Editorial managers
Translation	Design	Community	Multilingualism	Translators
Collaboration Tools	Design	Internal	Coordination	OPERAS members
Open Book Collective	Initial assessment	Managed	Revenue Mgmt.	TBD
NERD	Initial assessment	Managed	Analytics	TBD

The lifecycle of OPERAS services comprises multiple stages:

- Initial assessment (To avoid any confusion with the UCD stage that holds a different meaning, the official stage name, "Evaluation", has been changed for the

purpose of the UCQ-FRAME to "Initial assessment", which involves initial discussions and documentation for a specific opportunity);

- Design - approved phase where service design and development begin;
- Alpha - represents a prototype being tested on a limited scale;
- Beta - indicates a version available for wider scale testing;
- Production - signifies a feature-complete version with defined service management aspects;
- Discontinued - means the service is no longer available for new customers but still accessible to legacy users, and finally;
- Retired - indicates that the service is no longer available or in use by anyone.

As OPERAS is home to diverse teams, with different professional and scientific backgrounds, skills and capabilities, but a shared mission and vision, it is very important to establish coordination and alignment among project teams to ensure a coherent and integrated approach to service design. Because of many different ways to conduct user UX research and design, embracing a new project can be complicated even for experienced individuals or teams. Within this framework, incorporating a user-centred design approach in designing, ordering or managing different services, we will assist project teams in effectively addressing the needs and gathering feedback of their users and other stakeholders.

1.1 Introducing the UCQ-FRAME

The OPERAS-PLUS *D6.1 Common framework defining the methodology for achieving user-centred quality objectives* is a methodological framework designed to outline the principles, methodologies, and practices of UX research and UCD that should be considered to achieve successful projects (Part A). Additionally, UCQ-FRAME includes a number of recognised and commonly employed UX methods, techniques, and tools. Some of these have either been utilised in previous OPERAS projects or are considered suitable within the specific context of designing open scholarly communication tools and services (Part B). Both parts of UCQ-FRAME will facilitate project partners and the OPERAS community in scaling up user research and user-centred approach in order to (continuously) improve existing and build new innovative services that support and accelerate open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area.

The UCQ-FRAME combines UX and UCD methodologies and methods by implementing two approaches. The first, the bottom-up approach, focuses on existing OPERAS user-centred practices, as evidenced in published artefacts such as reports, deliverables, service blueprints, technical documentation, tutorials, guides, references, and presentations. Additionally, relevant artefacts generated by marketplaces and projects like EOSC and SSHOC are considered. The second, top-down approach, involves locating, adapting, and integrating various resources, including applicable standards, guidelines, and user-centred design principles. Furthermore, existing scientific knowledge,

academic sources, industry perspectives, and best practices are considered in this approach. By incorporating both the bottom-up and top-down approaches, the UCQ-FRAME will ensure a well-rounded integration of different UCD and UX methodologies and methods to support OPERAS in becoming an even more influential Research Infrastructure (RI), ultimately aiming to become an ERIC.

The purpose of the UCQ-FRAME is to offer state-of-the-art usability and user experience knowledge and methods, and practical steps that can be implemented to incorporate user-centred design principles into the process of planning, (re)designing, testing, evaluating, and monitoring OPERAS services.

By following and implementing the framework, we will more effectively support the organisation in meeting the needs and requirements of end-users. Moreover, we recognise that end-users have needs and motivations beyond their interactions with a product or service. While it is important to note that UCQ-FRAME cannot comprehensively address every conceivable aspect of usability and user experience research and design, we aim to provide a useful starting point for applying UCD and to *democratise* user research within the OPERAS community by offering PWDR¹, even though they are not (user) researchers by profession, support, training and guidance to expand their research skills and tools. It is crucial to emphasise that the initial set of methods, techniques, and tools can and should be customised or revised to align with the specific context of their application. By doing so, we anticipate that this framework will enhance the overall quality of OPERAS' existing and future services.

UX in a rapidly evolving open scholarly communication landscape strives to embrace innovation, while remaining sensitive to core human values, despite shifting technological and social trends, by placing the end-user in the centre of the discovery and design processes. The UCQ-FRAME is a “living entity” that will undergo regular updates throughout the project implementation, ensuring it is tailored to the evolving needs and progress of the project and of the OPERAS community as a whole. The present version of the living document represents a first version of the UCQ-FRAME and will be iteratively experimented and revised throughout the project’s duration.

1.2 UX and UCD in the context of OPERAS-PLUS

In recent decades, numerous design processes, frameworks and problem-solving methodologies have emerged, initially gaining traction in the private sector with a particular emphasis on commercial products and services. One prominent area of practice involves designing solutions “for and with users”, prioritising iterative piloting and testing to ensure efficient and effective problem resolution. These approaches have become very popular in complex and rapidly changing environments where the shift

¹ World Leaders in Research-Based User Experience. ‘Democratize User Research in 5 Steps’. Nielsen Norman Group, <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/democratize-user-research/>. Accessed 19 April 2023.

towards agile methodologies, frequent prototyping, and testing was driven by the need for more adaptable, user-centric, and efficient development practices that embrace uncertainty and promote continuous learning and improvement. In the meantime, these approaches have extended beyond their initial domains and found widespread application across diverse sectors and broader purposes due to obvious values of operationalising user research within and across an organisation. Notably, they have also gained significant popularity in the public sector and for developing impactful services and policies (Munger and van Deal 2020).

UX is a widely used term within the HCI community, also applied in various fields and industries, closely associated with user-centred design and the concept of usability. UCD, introduced by Norman and Draper in 1986, highlights the importance of developing products or services that meet user needs and requirements, and ensure "ease of use" (Norman & Draper, 1986). During the 1990s, Norman proposed the term "user experience" as a means to broaden the limited scope of usability, which primarily concentrated on cognitive processes, task efficiency, and work-related activities (Norman et al. 1995). Presently, it is widely accepted among researchers and practitioners that user experience emerges from the interplay of at least three key elements: the user, the system, and the context. Taking this perspective, Hassenzahl and Tractinsky (2006) define user experience as "a consequence of a user's internal state (predispositions, expectations, needs, motivation, mood, etc.), the characteristics of the designed system (e.g., complexity, purpose, usability, functionality, etc.) and the context (or the environment) within which the interaction occurs."

It is important to note that no single definition of user experience exists. As an alternative, Norman's definition can be considered: "No product is an island. A product is more than the product. It is a cohesive, integrated set of experiences. Think through all of the stages of a product or service – from initial intentions through final reflections, from the first usage to help, service, and maintenance. Make them all work together seamlessly." (The Interaction Design Foundation n.d.)

The scholarly literature highlights the growing significance of UX methodologies and UCD perspectives in open scholarly publishing and communication projects. These approaches are primarily employed in the (re)design of various products, services, and processes, including:

- Transforming traditional publications, such as books and journal articles, to align with user expectations.
- Enhancing the user experience of reading devices
- Developing user-friendly scholarly communication and publishing tools, e.g.
 - (Collaborative) Typesetting tools
 - Presentation tools
 - Manuscript managers
 - Research impact trackers

- Reference managers
- Creating digital libraries and library publishing services that cater to user needs.
- Improving institutional repositories to facilitate easy access, dissemination and archival of scholarly content.
- Streamlining the peer-review process to enhance user satisfaction.
- Implementing effective discovery services to enable users to find relevant scholarly resources.
- Prioritising accessibility and inclusion in scholarly communication platforms.
- Promoting data sharing and reuse practices to facilitate collaboration and knowledge dissemination.

UX and UCD methodologies have gained significant prominence in European Commission funded projects, also in those associated with pan-European initiatives and research infrastructures that promote data-driven and cross-disciplinary Open Science (OS). Projects such as EOSC Enhance² have incorporated a UX design methodology, establishing a structured process divided into distinct stages (Discovery, Conceptualisation, and Delivery). This methodology allows for the evaluation of existing functionalities, identification of emerging requirements, and implementation of service enhancements to continuously improve their offerings.³ On the other hand, certain OPERAS projects, such as TRIPLE⁴, have been inspired by user-centred and co-design approaches in developing solutions within the SSH academic and research community. Instead of relying solely on detached expert insights, their approach aimed to foster more human-centric solutions and actively involve users and other stakeholders, including about 1700 participants, in the (co)design process of the GoTriple multilingual and multicultural discovery platform (Dumouchel et al. 2020).

In OPERAS-PLUS, we leverage the advancements made in related fields and projects, tailoring these approaches to our unique context. This involves considering our specific context: our users have specific needs and goals and perform certain tasks within a specific environment in which OPERAS services will be utilised. By taking these factors into account, we will ensure that our efforts align with the specific requirements of our target users and effectively address their needs within our methodological framework. Such an approach to implementing the aforementioned methodologies is well in line

² EOSC Enhance: Connecting Thematic Communities to Advance Open Science, <https://eosc-portal.eu/about/enhance>

³ EOSC Enhance: D4.2 UX model and verification for EOSC Portal development (update). https://eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/D4.2%20UX%20model%20and%20verification%20for%20EOSC%20Portal%20development%20v1.0_Final.pdf

⁴ Triple – Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration'. Accessed 24 April 2023. <https://project.gotriple.eu/>.

with the OPERAS goals of making “Open Science a reality for research in SSH and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, students and more generally the whole society across Europe and worldwide, without barriers.” (Schulte and Caliman 2023).

In case of any gaps or misunderstandings in the UCQ-FRAME, a recognised family of standards (ISO 9241) provides a solid foundation. The ISO family 9241, particularly ISO 9241-210 (2019) and ISO 9241-11 (2018), offers well-established terms, definitions, principles, and processes that serve as a reliable reference in cases of uncertainty or disagreement. Additionally, the UCQ-FRAME aligns with widely accepted best practices in the UX profession (User Experience Professionals Association - UXPA⁵; International Usability & User Experience Qualification Board - UXQB⁶) and ResearchOps community.

1.3 Benefits of the UCQ-FRAME

The organisation's interests and business objectives must also be considered to create benefits for end-users. During the development of new solutions, user-centred design aims to balance the three competing forces of desirability, feasibility, and viability (Figure 2). In order to achieve the best possible results from the proposed solution, it is important to harmonise all three factors, ensuring a compelling case for change that addresses both the human and organisational dimensions.

Desirable: Can people use it? Does it provide solutions to current issues? Is the solution reliable? Is it easy to use? Is it appropriate based on cultural context?

Viable: Is it within the organisation's budget? Is the proposed business model viable? Will the initiative gain approval, support, and endorsement from governing bodies and other stakeholders?

Feasible: Is it technically feasible for the organisation to complete, with the available resources and expertise to support its implementation? Does it identify obstacles that can realistically be overcome?

⁵User Experience Professionals Association (UXPA). Accessed 24 April 2023. <https://uxpa.org/>.

⁶International Usability & User Experience Qualification Board (UXQB). UXQB. Accessed 24 April 2023. <https://uxqb.org/en/>.

Figure 2: Desirability, feasibility, and viability: the sweet spot for innovation

Integrating the UCQ-FRAME within multiple levels of the OPERAS governance structure, encompassing OPERAS AISBL, SAC, EA, OCT, STB, and AoC, is very important. The widespread adoption of the framework throughout the Association will yield benefits across various areas, including the following:

- Minimising unintended, biased, or self-oriented design (“ego-design”): By considering the potential effects of design decisions and acknowledging that project team members or designers/developers are not the end-users, the framework helps prevent design choices that may not meet user needs.
- Reducing development and operational costs: By enabling users and stakeholders to perform tasks more efficiently, effectively, and with greater satisfaction, the framework contributes to cost savings in both the development and operational stages.
- Mitigating risks: The structured process provided by the framework increases the likelihood of creating usable and successful products or services, thereby reducing the risks associated with bad user experience.
- Formulating a user-centric product or service strategy: Developing a strategy across OPERAS services that puts users at the centre enhances the chances of success in relevant marketplaces and attracts and engages a larger user base.
- Understanding user needs and fostering continuous improvement: By gaining

insights into user behaviour and developing services that address those needs, OPERAS can respond to new information on an ongoing basis, enabling continuous improvement and adaptation.

- Barrier-free and inclusive solutions: By taking care of people with different types of abilities we create content and solutions that are accessible to as many people as possible.
- Promoting ethical design and respecting user privacy: By prioritising user privacy and trust, effective UX design practices within OPERAS can be achieved.
- Increasing UX maturity: By focusing on enhancing UX maturity, defining service offerings, and incorporating leading practices, OPERAS ensures that high-impact projects are making progress in these areas.
- Proactive user feedback collection and satisfaction assessment: By ensuring that services receive valuable user feedback and actively assess user satisfaction, OPERAS can make informed decisions to continuously elevate the user experience with services in different development phases.

1.4 Relationships with other OPERAS-PLUS work packages and deliverables

The close linkage between "WP6: User engagement and training," "WP4: OPERAS Innovation Lab development," and "WP5: Technical support to OPERAS services" within the broader context of "Pillar 2: Services Management" highlights the natural integration of user-centric practices. We recommend aligning future user-related activities and practices with the OPERAS Innovation Observatory (WP4) and the Service and Technology Board (WP5) to enhance this synergy. This alignment is crucial for promoting a user-centric culture and facilitating the development of user-oriented infrastructure and services within OPERAS.

WP6 activities play an important role in the communication and impact assessment efforts of WP8. They promote effective communication with key stakeholders, leadership, and external communities, ensuring the sharing of updates, progress, challenges, and outcomes of UCD and UX-related initiatives within OPERAS. These activities also provide valuable opportunities to gather feedback contributing to continuous improvement within the organisation.

WP6 is also closely connected to WP7, "Support to national nodes", promoting a close relationship with local communities. Both work packages foster strong connections with local communities and OPERAS national nodes. We strive to understand their needs, deliver services, and provide training as part of our OPERAS-PLUS collaborative efforts. Through active engagement, we strengthen our connection and ensure that our initiatives meet their specific requirements.

Creating strong connections between work packages is crucial for democratising the UCD and UX approach in the OPERAS community. We will enhance and adapt the UCQ-FRAME in Task 6.3 through testing and feedback from different WP partners. This

iterative process will guarantee its efficacy and relevance for selected services, promoting a collaborative and inclusive UCD and UX approach across the OPERAS community.

1.5 How to use the UCQ-FRAME

This framework is intended for all OPERAS members who ...

- Desire to position the user at the core of the innovation process.
- Seek a deeper understanding of users' thoughts, emotions, and interactions with various systems or services.
- Aim to gather user insights and make informed decisions by focusing on the users' priorities and engaging with them in their natural environment.
- Aspire to gain a deeper understanding of the organisation's role within the constantly evolving scholarly communication landscape.

The UCQ-FRAME helps to ...

- Discover strategies for gaining insights, understanding, and connecting with users.
- Explore various methods to empathise with users effectively.
- Learn approaches to make sense of user data and transform it into actionable insights.

The UX and UCD principles and practices outlined in this document offer a fundamental understanding of the involved processes, methodologies, philosophies, and mindsets, ultimately aiming to optimise user engagement across various OPERAS services (**Part A**). The methodology presented is specifically adapted to suit the unique context of OPERAS. Through careful evaluation, we have identified a range of widely used UX methods and tools deemed suitable for achieving the objectives of OPERAS-PLUS. These methods are recommended rather than imposed, as they align to develop user-centric open scholarly communication services that consolidate resources from across Europe via a single access point (**Part B**). We have incorporated methods that:

- gather data about users, including their interactions, behaviours, emotions, beliefs, meanings, and/or values,
- offer a framework for organising or structuring the collected data,
- visualise the complex user-centred design process, and
- have been employed in various OPERAS projects, by complementary research infrastructures, or within the realm of scholarly communication.

It is important to acknowledge that the methods in this document are only recommendations among countless other approaches. Furthermore, these examples should be critically examined concerning the specific contexts and target groups in which they will be applied. They can be combined, adapted, or enhanced while preserving the core principle of user experience and user-centred design.

The UCQ-FRAME is inspired by the Double Diamond 2.0 design process, incorporating new elements such as design principles, method banks, and a culture of innovation to guide a structured approach to problem identification and solution development. The UCQ-FRAME encompasses diverse methods carefully organised to align with each phase of the design process, enabling a comprehensive and systematic approach to user-centred design in open scholarly communication. Double Diamond is a well-known metaphor and process model in design thinking that was created in 2004 by the [British Design Council](#) and adopted in the workflows of many organisations and companies.

Figure 3: Double Diamond (Adapted from Design Council. Licensed under CC BY 4.0.)

Below, the methods are presented alphabetically for ease of reference. In the later implementation and validation phase, we will explore the most suitable categorisation for these methods to ensure optimal organisation. Organising methods using this or any other approach may not be perfect, as project processes, development, or design phases/activities can be ambiguous and vary between projects. Additionally, due to the iterative nature of the design process, the same methods might be employed in different design stages. This challenge was addressed by incorporating dotted arrows to represent iterations and mapping Double Diamond phases with the user-centred

design cycle, which, with minor adjustments, essentially aligns with any existing development or design approaches (e.g. Design Thinking, Design Sprints, Agile, Scrum, Lean UX, etc.).⁷

Enhancing validity through methodological triangulation

One way to improve the validity of the work is by selecting methods based on the specific context and user groups, and by employing methodological triangulation. This involves combining multiple methods within a single design project to gather a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. To achieve this, the aim is to apply more than one method, which collectively capture the following aspects:

- User's Feedback: Focus on what the user says about their needs, preferences, and experiences (what the user **SAYS, THINKS**)
- User's Actions: Observe and analyse what the users do while interacting with the product or service (what the user **DOES**)
- Contextual and Cognitive Insights: Gather information about the user's physical, perceptual, and cognitive context during their interaction with a product or service

Visual keys in the UCQ-FRAME

Boxes - emphasising important points.

Definition - a crucial definition fundamental for utilising the framework, highlighted in bold throughout the document.

Tips - recommended UCD and user research approaches (worth noting).

Methods and tools - Integrated UX methods and tools.

⁷ Covering in detail various project management processes and models is beyond the scope of this deliverable.

Part A – Common Framework Defining the Methodology for Achieving User-Centred Quality Objectives

2. UCD principles and UX process cycle

Norman and Draper (1986) profoundly impacted the design field with their seminal work on **UCD**. They emphasised the importance of anchoring product development to user needs, engaging users throughout the design process, paying close attention to activity analysis, and conducting iterative system evaluations from the early design stages. Roughly a decade later, the UCD methodology was formalised in the international standard ISO 13407 (1999), predominantly focusing on creating usable systems. In subsequent revisions in 2010 and 2019, the standard incorporated the notion of user experience.⁸

UX refers to the unique human experience that occurs before, during and after interactions with systems, products, or services. UX research and design aims to optimise this experience by proactively considering it prior to product development. UX design focuses on developing products that harmonise user needs and desires with business objectives. By prioritising users, one can create products or services that are economically feasible and hold genuine value for the target audience. UX is a holistic field that extends beyond being a standalone end-result (Bluestone 2019). It integrates process, methodology, and mindset to enable optimal user engagement across various platforms and devices. UX goes beyond aesthetic design or basic usability, emphasising strategic planning and meaningful interaction. The user experience honeycomb is a classic diagram introduced by Peter Morville (2004) to highlight the various facets of UX design. The honeycomb is a great starting point that identifies an optimal balance among the different areas that contribute to a good user experience with what the users **think** about the product's value, usability and usefulness; **feel** regarding its usefulness and desirability; and its accessibility, credibility, and findability during actual **use** (Figure

⁸ The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) established the ISO 9241 series of standards, comprising international guidelines and requirements for designing and evaluating interactive systems, including software and hardware. These standards address numerous aspects of usability and UCD. The ISO 9241 family of standards includes several individual standards, each with a specific focus. The ISO 9241 series of standards is well-known and employed by designers, developers, and usability experts globally to enhance the usability and efficiency of interactive systems. The ISO standards are expensive. To minimise expenses, consider reading David Travis' thorough summary of the ISO 9241 series before buying the complete set; despite being slightly outdated, it offers a valuable overview.

4).

Figure 4: Peter Morville's User Experience Honeycomb (with minor modification by Katerina Karagianni, 2018)

For effective user experience design, it's crucial to understand the essence of UX and its function in the design process. This involves grounding the work in core UCD concepts and principles (the WHY), as well as process cycles, methods/tools, and deliverables (the HOW) outlined in the framework.⁹ Following OPERAS' commitment to fostering positive change in the world through values such as the common good (achieved through open scholarly communication and publishing in SSH), diversity and inclusion (including multilingualism and multiculturalism), and democracy (achieved through open access), we recognize the significance of empowering users and involving them in decision-making processes. A fundamental principle of UX design emphasises the active participation of users/participants in the design process from an early stage. This approach enables designers to effectively address users' specific needs and preferences, democratising the design process and fostering emancipation. By providing users with a seat at the table, we aim to create an inclusive environment where their voices are heard, and their perspectives shape the development of our services. Consequently, the

⁹ In this framework, 'design' encompasses the entire project process rather than a single stage, extending beyond cosmetic aspects and representing the cumulative effect of all decisions shaping the final system, product or service.

UX design process and associated methods are rooted in the user-centred design, also known as HCD. User- and human-centred design are frequently used as synonyms, though some believe they carry distinct meanings. Instead of conducting an in-depth comparison between the two concepts in this framework, we have embraced user-centred design as our approach. This approach focuses on identifying and prioritising relevant users and user groups within OPERAS' target audiences.

2.1 Foundational concepts related to the UCD process

This section, mainly based on the ISO 9241 series of standards, presents and defines the terms that form the building blocks of the methodological framework.¹⁰ Examining these concepts aims to create a solid foundation for upcoming chapters. These chapters will introduce and discuss additional concepts and methods essential to planning the user-centred design process and implementing user experience research and design in various problem/challenge-driven or solution/outcome-driven projects.

11:2018).

Human-centred design is an “approach to systems design and development that aims to make interactive systems more usable by focusing on the use of the system and applying human factors/ergonomics and usability knowledge and techniques” (ISO 9241-

According to ISO 9241-220 (2019), the primary objective of following the HCD principles and approaches is to enhance “human-centred quality” as a measure of the degree to which an interactive system has fulfilled the user requirements.¹¹ The following chapters will delve deeper into user-centred design principles and practices.

Human-centred quality is the “extent to which requirements for usability, accessibility, user experience and avoidance of harm from use are met” (ISO 9241-220:2019).

Human- or user-centred quality objectives outline what an interactive system should accomplish for its users related to four key aspects that ensure the system, product or service meets the users' needs, expectations, and well-being. These objectives are set during the planning phase but can be adjusted as a deeper understanding of the user's context is obtained. They assist stakeholders in prioritising user needs throughout the project, and it's ideal to involve users in the project (team) from the beginning.

¹⁰ Within this context, our primary reliance is on three standards: ISO 9241-11:2018, which provides guidance on usability; ISO 9241-110:220, which outlines dialogue principles for electronic displays; and ISO 9241-210:2019, which focuses on human-centred design for interactive systems.

¹¹ Besides user- or human-centred quality, there are other quality dimensions, such as technology-centred quality and business-centred quality.

Examples of user-centred quality objectives, framed as informed hypotheses, address various challenges related to scholarly communication practices:

- Authors should be able to submit their papers in less than 5 minutes (usability, efficiency)
- Authors should receive an automated email notification acknowledging their submission and supplementary information regarding the review process (usability, effectiveness)
- Reviewers of an OJS-hosted journal should encounter a seamless and user-friendly review process that meets their expectations (usability, satisfaction)
- After submitting a paper, authors should feel confident that the journal is trustworthy and adheres to the latest open scholarly publishing and transparent peer-review practices (user experience)
- For low-vision or colour-blind readers, comprehension of charts and graphs should be made possible by providing supplementary audio recordings (accessibility)
- Authors should be aware of all applicable publishing charges before submitting a conference paper (avoidance of harm from use)

The objectives for users of the interactive system should be complemented by specific, actionable, and measurable criteria designed to accomplish these objectives. For example:

- Objective: Authors should be able to submit and upload their papers in less than 15 minutes (usability, efficiency)
- Criterion: Average time authors take to complete the submission process.
- Measurement: Set a target goal to decrease the average submission time to below 15 minutes, continuously observing and improving the submission workflow.
 - Perform an initial evaluation: Determine the current average submission time and pinpoint areas of concern or potential enhancements in the submission workflow (e.g., remote, moderated usability test).
 - Introduce progress indicators: Offer visual cues or progress bars showing each submission stage's status, enabling authors to monitor their progress and estimate the time left (e.g., prototyping, A/B testing).

Interactive system is a “combination of hardware and/or software and/or services and/or people that users interact with in order to achieve specific goals” (ISO 9241-11:2018; ISO 9241-210:2019)

Interactive systems allow users to exchange information with the system through the

user interface (UI). The UI offers various controls (UI elements) that enable users to interact with the system to complete their specific tasks effectively, efficiently, and satisfactorily. Some user interface elements may or may not be interactive, for example, hyperlinks or paragraphs of text.

Service is a “means of delivering value for the customer by facilitating results the customer to achieve” (ISO 9241:11)

Organisations provide services that offer new value propositions to their users, often leveraging novel technologies or business models across various touchpoints and platforms. Services can include human-system interactions, for example, a researcher accessing the online submission system of a journal, and human-human interactions, for example, a journal editor engaging in discussion with the peer reviewer to refine the research work during the peer review process. In the literature, services are commonly defined as intangible and experiential offerings provided by one party to another and consumed upon delivery. At the same time, products refer to tangible items that can be possessed. To simplify the understanding of this distinction, it is helpful to contrast service design with product design. Product designers focus on creating tangible objects like cars, planes, or laptops. In contrast, service designers are responsible for crafting intangible experiences, such as the interactions involved in obtaining a driver's licence or booking a flight using a laptop, and designing “the behind the scene activities that enable those experiences to be delivered as planned” (Dervojeda et al. 2014).

Usability is the “extent to which a system, product or service can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use” (ISO 9241-11:2018).

This usability definition covers a few important terms. **Effectiveness** is related to “accuracy and completeness with which users achieve specified goals” (for instance, it can be measured by the task success rate; the number of interaction errors), **efficiency** to “resources used in relation to the results achieved” (e.g. time; human effort or resources used to achieve a goal; time on errors; the number of help requests; the number of input errors; system failures) and **satisfaction** to the “extent to which the user's physical, cognitive and emotional responses that result from the use of a system, product or service meet the user's needs and expectations” (ISO 9241-11:2018). Effectiveness and efficiency can impact satisfaction and, consequently, user experience. On the other hand, satisfaction levels (e.g. the number of users expressing frustration) or the percentage of unfavourable user feedback may cause users to either abandon a task or take longer than expected to complete it. To assess satisfaction, researchers frequently use (standardised) surveys like the SUS (System Usability Scale). The SUS evaluates a user's subjective perception of usability, concentrating on aspects like ease of use, learnability, efficiency, and overall satisfaction with the system. With scores ranging from 0 to 100, it helps compare different systems, where higher scores indicate better usability.

User experience is “user’s perceptions and responses that result from the use and/or anticipated use of a system, product or service” ISO 9241-210 (2019)

The ISO standards attempt to differentiate the concepts of UX and usability by focusing on objectively measurable factors in the definition of usability while emphasising the subjective nature of experience in the definition of UX. However, most experts concur that UX is a broader concept, with usability being a component of the overall user experience (Travis 2014).

The user's perception and responses, as further explained by the ISO standard, encompass their “emotions, beliefs, preferences, perceptions, comfort, behaviours, and accomplishments” that occur before, during, and after usage. User experience is an outcome of various factors such as brand image, presentation, functionality, system performance, interactive behaviour, and support features of a system, product, or service. Unlike usability, which primarily focuses on the pragmatic aspects of interaction, user experience also delves into hedonic qualities. As Hassenzahl (2008) indicated in his model, a positive user experience arises when users not only accomplish pragmatic or instrumental “do-goals” but also satisfy “be-goals” related to the fulfilment of fundamental human needs. Upon attaining these be-goals during interaction with a system, users associate hedonic attributes with it, enhancing their overall experience. User surveys such as the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) can effectively evaluate different aspects of user experience (Laugwitz et al. 2008). The questionnaire features 26 bipolar items within six UEQ scales, evaluating constructs like *attractiveness*, *efficiency*, *perspicuity*, *dependability*, *stimulation*, and *novelty*. These scales assess pragmatic qualities (usability) and hedonic aspects of user experience, with attractiveness reflecting the overall impression of an interactive system's quality (Schrepp 2021).

Based on the ISO 9241 series of standards, H. Miki (2014) has developed an integrated evaluation framework for usability and UX by replacing *satisfaction* with subjective UX measures (*perceived quality*, *perceived value*, and *satisfaction*) while retaining *effectiveness* and *efficiency* as objective usability measures (Figure 5). He suggests no direct relationship exists between the two usability factors and subjective UX measures, but the connections between them can be strengthened if the usability measures are well-designed. His framework aligns with the broader notion that usability and UX are related but separate concepts, emphasising the need to consider both usability and UX measures to achieve a holistic understanding of the user experience.

Figure 5: Integrated evaluation framework of usability and UX (H. Miki 2014)

Accessibility is the “extent to which products, systems, services, environments and facilities can be used by people from a population with the widest range of user needs, characteristics and capabilities to achieve identified goals in identified contexts of use” (ISO 9241-210 (2019))

While various services provide significant benefits to most users such as convenience, speed, choice, or low cost, certain groups may require assistance or additional resources to access them due to physical or cognitive disabilities, learning difficulties, lack of knowledge or skills, limited technology or internet access, language, cultural, or paywall barriers. When discussing accessibility, the focus is often on preventing the (un)intentional creation of systems that are challenging or impossible for some individuals due to assumptions about users' physical or cognitive abilities.

Accessibility involves:

- facilitating the use of products or services by providing access through different channels,
- adapting content or user interfaces, or
- offering additional support to make products or services available to the broadest possible audience.

By adhering to accessibility standards (ISO 9231-171:2008) or WCAG 2.1 (2018), which are legally enforced in some countries or markets, one can help achieve this goal. Many checklists use the WCAG as a standard for assessing compliance with accessibility requirements and classifying accessibility into three levels: A: Essential; AA: Ideal Support; and AAA: Specialised Support. Although striving for "perfect accessibility" is respectable, it is essential to acknowledge that reaching 100% accessibility is not realistically attainable due to many contextual factors.

Avoidance of harm of use is the extent to which "negative consequences regarding health, safety, finances or the environment that result from use of the system" are minimised (ISO 9241-220:2018)

2.2 Guiding UCD principles

The updated ISO 9241-210 (2019) standard builds upon the previous versions and further expands core UCD principles and activities by acknowledging that user experience comprises multiple elements, including aesthetics, emotions, and satisfaction. It highlights the importance of considering the holistic experience of users during their interaction with a product or service. By following UCD principles and a methodical process to steer uncertainty, designers can create products or services that meet functional and usability requirements while delivering a positive, lasting user experience, increasing user satisfaction and loyalty.

The principles established in the latest ISO 9241-210 (2019) standard guide designers in developing user-centric designs that emphasise user requirements, integrate user input, and provide outstanding user experiences. The following Table 3 details the six principles identified by this standard.

Table 2: Six UCD principles (ISO 9241-210 2019)

	<p>The design process relies on a clear understanding of users, their tasks, and their environments</p>	<p>This principle emphasises understanding the users' 'context of use': it is crucial to know the users, their goals, tasks, resources, and the environment in which they operate. For instance, the standard highlights the difference between a system targeting a student searching for an open digital collection on a mobile phone or a researcher using an organisation's</p>
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		<p>infrastructure for retrieving a large data set via a provided API. An excellent experience for one may not be suitable for the other.</p>
	<p>Users are actively involved throughout the whole design and development process</p>	<p>This principle underlines the importance of engaging users in the design and development process, as they offer valuable insights into the context of use, tasks, and how users are expected to interact with the upcoming product, system, or service. For example, involving researchers from various SSH disciplines in diverse user research activities, such as contextual interviews or co-design sessions, enables designers to observe people in action and understand their specific needs, goals, tasks, and practices. These insights can guide the development of solutions that align with relevant researchers' objectives.</p>
	<p>The design is driven and refined by user-centred evaluation</p>	<p>This principle highlights the importance of tailoring every phase of the development process to create an artefact based on insights obtained from earlier stages, ensuring it can be efficiently used and tested by people in the most realistic ways possible. For example, imagine a research platform in the initial design phase. The researchers can interact with the prototype and offer insights into its functionality, interface, and overall user experience. The design team actively engages researchers by conducting user-centred evaluations, such as usability testing or user feedback sessions.</p>
	<p>The process is iterative, involving continuous refinement and improvement</p>	<p>Iterative development, as seen in various agile methodologies like Scrum or Kanban, is now standard practice in project management, especially in the software development industry. User-centred design works best when implemented through a series of iterations, each following similar steps. Each iteration improves and expands</p>

		<p>upon the results of its predecessor. It is also considered a risk-reduction strategy, where iterative design and development focus on rapid delivery and reducing the feedback loop length commonly associated with the traditional waterfall development process. Building upon the example from the previous principle, the design team would utilise the insights gathered from usability tests and feedback sessions. They would then undertake an iterative process of refining the solution, incorporating the received feedback, and making enhancements to address any identified issues or concerns raised by the researchers. This iterative design and testing cycle would continue until the design team is satisfied with the final solution, ensuring that it aligns effectively with the needs and preferences of the targeted user-groups.</p>
	<p>The design focuses on the whole user experience</p>	<p>This principle emphasises that user-centred design encompasses more than just usability, extending to the whole user experience. This involves not only the effectiveness and efficiency in accomplishing goals but also the emotional response and the overall influence on the user's life. It is vital to consider various aspects of the user's experience, including anticipatory, episodic, and cumulative experiences. Furthermore, elements such as mastery, autonomy, and purpose play a significant role in the user's wellbeing and must be considered when designing a product or system.</p>
	<p>The design team includes multidisciplinary skills and perspectives</p>	<p>This principle states that the team must maintain a balance, with enough members to include diverse skills and viewpoints but not so many that communication becomes difficult. Essential roles within the group should consist of user researchers or people who do research (PWDR), interaction</p>

		<p>designers, content creators, developers, and others. Each member should bring their unique abilities and traits to enhance the team's collective knowledge and experience. Encouraging collaboration and effective communication within this diverse group allows the organisation to optimise innovation and success in transforming a product or service from its initial concept to a finished solution.</p>
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2.3 UCD process cycle

The user-centred design focuses on planning for iteration, gathering user feedback early and often, and taking action based on that feedback. Consequently, the user-centred design process consists of a four-stage iterative cycle, with the planning phase and the delivered solution meeting user requirements positioned outside the main rectangle (Figure 6). The four primary activities are iterative, depicted by dotted arrows, and each stage employs existing user experience methods and tools, sometimes different and sometimes same, to produce different UCD deliverables and reach set goals. Part B of this framework details these methods, tools, and deliverables.

The box surrounding the four activities in the figure indicates that user-centred design can start at any point ('Understand the context of use,' 'Specify the user requirements,' 'Design solution,' or 'Evaluate the design') depending on the project. No matter the starting point, a clear understanding of the context of use is essential. For example, if the context of use, especially users and their tasks, is well-documented from a previous project, the project begins by specifying user requirements. On the other hand, if users' express dissatisfaction with an existing system and the context of use is well-known, the project starts with systematically evaluating the system.

Figure 6: The UCD process and activities according to ISO 9231-210 standard (modified)

The UCD process cycles are designed to be flexible, adaptable, and inclusive, enabling the integration of various existing and widespread methodologies, frameworks, practices, and approaches to address specific project requirements. Examples include integrating agile development practices, lean, design thinking, and other models or frameworks.

Organisations can develop a comprehensive design approach by leveraging the compatibility and openness of UCD processes, merging the most effective elements from various methods to deliver systems, products and services that offer the best user experiences. For example, in the UCQ-FRAME, we have combined UCD with the Double Diamond v2.0 framework (Figure 3), emphasising the iterative exploration of multiple options and refining them to identify the optimal solution. This approach enables us to depict the divergent-convergent nature of the design process (Figure 6), also highlighting the importance of user engagement. By establishing connections with users and stakeholders, we can promote innovation, encourage organisational culture change, and strengthen internal capacity.

Despite various models or frameworks using distinct names for their phases or stages, it's essential to recognize that well-known approaches like UCD and the Double Diamond share core principles. Consequently, these stages can be aligned and seamlessly integrated into almost any existing lifecycle, specifically, in our case, the current OPERAS service design and development lifecycle (Table 3).

Table 3: OPERAS service design and development lifecycle

Step	UCD cycle	Double Diamond cycle	Current OPERAS service development cycle
1	Plan the UCD process	Problem/Challenge	Initial assessment (Evaluation)
2	Understanding and specifying the context of use	Discover (research, synthesise)	Design
3	Specifying the user requirements	Define	
4	Producing design solutions	Design (ideate, prototype, test)	Alpha
5	Evaluating design	Deliver (refine, build, implement)	Beta
6	Designed solution meets user requirements	Solution/Outcome (measure, feedback, analyse, improve)	Production

The simplest version of this adapted model, which places the user at the core of the design and development process, would involve an iterative cycle consisting of following phases (Figure 7):

- Planning - scope, team, stakeholder support
- User research - understand, specify, explore, research, discover, synthesise, define
 - Begin user research to understand the context and target audience's needs, goals, limitations, expectations, and tasks.
- Design - ideate, generate, make, prototype, test
 - Use research insights to create ideas and early design concepts. Apply prototyping for visual and interactive exploration.
- Evaluation - deliver (refine, build, implement), measure (feedback, analyse, improve)

- Capture user feedback and assess UX continuously throughout the project, ensuring ongoing improvement and alignment with user needs.

Figure 7: Basic UCD process

2.3.1 ResearchOps: supporting and operationalising the UCD process

The UCQ-FRAME also integrates the ResearchOps framework, which has gained recognition and adoption within the user research and UX community, embraced by various organisations and companies to support and streamline research operations.¹² The framework was formulated based on data gathered from over 300 survey responses and insights derived from 33 workshops. One of the results was a map that pinpoints and charts diverse elements, attributes, processes, and interactions associated with ResearchOps within an organisation (Figure 8).

¹² Established by Kate Towsey, Research Operations Manager at Atlassian, the community has since expanded to encompass more than 16,000 members. URL: <https://medium.com/researchops-community/creating-impact-with-research-ops-leveraging-the-power-of-communities-1a55b2f14692>

Figure 8: ResearchOps map. Source: Kate Towsey

After these workshops, the emphasis pivoted to outlining their comprehension of ResearchOps, leading to the following definition:

“ResearchOps (re+ops) ”includes the methods and tactics that drive user research and sets up essential roles, tools, and processes that assist researchers in distributing and amplifying the influence of their work across an organization” (Boulton 2019a).

The ResearchOps framework consists of eight pillars, supporting and operationalising the UCD process (Figure 9). This integration establishes standardised processes and offers a structured approach for implementing, managing, scaling, and assessing user research activities within and across OPERAS. Understanding these core components allows us to examine ways to seamlessly operationalise research practices in any organisation (Boulton 2019b).

How research is systematised

Tools and infrastructure

managing the tools, infrastructure, and technological components that support research operations

Governance

addresses legal and ethical considerations to protect both the organisation and the participants

Data and knowledge management

managing and organising user insights data, information and knowledge within the organisation

Recruitment and admin

managing the process of recruiting, coordinating, and administering participants for research activities

How research is supported

Environment

level of maturity of the research practice within an organization.

Scope

effectively managing research insights, processes, and methods across the entire organisation

People

building capacity, professional development and enhance research skills within the organisation

Organisational context

managing various aspects related to space, time, resources and budget that influence research activities

Figure 9: Adapted eight pillars of ResearchOps. Source: Emma Boulton

Research operations encompass all eight pillars of user research, making it seem complex and overwhelming at first glance.¹³ Each category on the list contains numerous sub-elements. The framework's complexity demonstrates the numerous factors to consider during user research within a UCD process; however, it is optional to address every aspect simultaneously. The approach depends on the organisation's

¹³ Organisations like the Norman Nielsen Group (Kaplan 2020) and Pistoia Alliance (UXLS Research Ops Framework 2023) have implemented ResearchOps to support and scale user research across various projects. They have customised the main components of ResearchOps to align with their specific requirements. For example, the Norman Nielsen Group identifies six components (Participants, Governance, Knowledge, Tools, Competency, Advocacy). In contrast, Pistoia Alliance proposes seven categories for building research operations in the life sciences (Environment & Organisational Context, UX Methods & Processes, UX Practitioners, Participants, Tools & Infrastructure, Regulatory & Compliance, Data & Knowledge Management). The variation in the number of categories reflects the renaming and merging of the original eight pillars to better fit their current practices and specific organisational needs and contexts.

structure and requirements and the user-centred work within it.

The eight user research pillars can be classified into "how research is supported" and "how research is systematised" within the organisation (Boulton 2019b). The first group includes the following categories (Figure 9):

1. Environment

- encompasses people silos, education, research value, buy-in, pushback, internally focused aspects, stakeholders, executives, and colleagues, highlighting research operations' vital role in facilitating and empowering effective research collaboration across teams, levels, and stakeholders.
- for example, promoting and spreading UX research within the OPERAS community from an educational, cultural, and environmental standpoint

2. Scope

- covers key themes such as cadence, sharing insights, prioritisation, integrating insights, processes, methods, and protocols, treating research as a team sport, emphasising the importance of effectively managing user research insights across the organisation, from generation to organisation, sharing, and integration into decision-making processes.
- for example, establishing a central OPERAS UX methods bank supported by a methods selection framework that takes into consideration various factors like service lifecycle phase or resources at hand.

3. People

- covers vital themes such as the community of practice, professional development, staffing, mature career paths, leadership, and organisational design, emphasising the importance of nurturing talent, fostering professional growth, and creating an environment that supports the development and advancement of UX professionals within the organisation.
- for example, hiring dedicated OPERAS UX practitioners to run research operations and organising training for non-UX'ers who want to apply user research methods in their projects.

4. Organisational Context

- covers aspects such as space, time, resources, budget, ROI, business constraints, market forces, and organisational UX maturity, conveying the concept of managing operational dynamics and factors influencing research activities within the organisation while emphasising the need for a holistic and conducive ecosystem for successful user research operations.
- for example, carrying out yearly UX maturity evaluations to monitor progress within OPERAS services and projects.

These pillars are where we need to start, as they pertain to how research is conducted.

By understanding the broader context of the research organisation, ResearchOps can have a significant impact. On the other hand, to achieve the most immediate effect in the short term, we can focus on the other four pillars related to "how research is conducted and systematised." The second group includes the following categories:

5. Recruitment and Administration

- covers key themes such as incentives, scheduling, logistics, panel management, paperwork, timesheets, and participant coordination, emphasising the importance of effectively managing the process of recruiting, coordinating, and administering participants for UCD activities while capturing the essential aspects related to participant management in a more intuitive and task-aligned manner.
- for example, establish a central OPERAS participants recruitment panel that enables engagement and communication (screening, invitation, scheduling sessions, thanking and incentive confirmation)

6. Data and Knowledge Management

- includes vital themes such as research library/repository, data silos, data gardening, document templates, and knowledge management, emphasising the importance of effectively managing and organising information and user insights within the organisation to foster accessibility, collaboration, and knowledge sharing, while the pillar suggests a centralised and dynamic repository of valuable resources that facilitates easy access to information and promotes innovation foster and a culture of continuous improvement.
- for example, using consistent file-naming conventions for easier discovery as was suggested in the [OPERAS-PLUS Data Management Plan](#) (Ernst 2023) or establishing the OPERAS research repository, which is the central place where stakeholders can find the latest research insights and reports from different research teams.

7. Governance

- covers key themes such as risk assessment, GDPR, legal, information/data security, consent, and ethics, emphasising the importance of compliance with regulations, privacy protection, and ethical standards in UCD and ResearchOps while highlighting the need for a robust governance framework that addresses legal and ethical considerations to safeguard both the organisation and participants involved in research activities.
- for example, establishing protocols and procedures to ensure data is collected, stored, and managed to protect participant privacy and comply with relevant laws, including the GDPR (e.g. DARIAH ELDAH's [Consent Form Wizard - CFW](#)); anonymisation, which involves removing or altering personally identifiable information; and pseudonymisation, which includes replacing or encrypting identifiable information with pseudonyms or

codes.

8. Tools and Infrastructure

- includes key themes such as procurement, software, hardware, labs, systems, technology, and networks, emphasising the importance of managing the tools, infrastructure, and technological components that support UCD and ResearchOps while highlighting the need for a comprehensive and efficient technology stack to facilitate research activities, data management, experimentation, and collaboration within the organisation.
- for example, collaborating with IT teams and project officers to guarantee that user researchers or PWDRs are equipped with the resources required for their tasks, such as IT/AV hardware/software for recording and analysing research data, designated physical or virtual spaces/labs for usability testing or eye-tracking, and more.

Many organisations often prioritise the aspects from the second group, concentrating on how research is conducted and systematised, which can lead to significant short-term gains in research operations.

As part of *Task 6.3: Implementation of the developed framework for selected OPERAS services* (and projects), our objective is to adapt and prioritise specific components of the research operations framework. This will be accomplished by surveying the existing user centred-design and user research activities, practices, and capacities within the broader OPERAS community. Additionally, we will evaluate OPERAS' current UX maturity level (e.g. Pernice et al. 2021). By leveraging the survey findings, we can prioritise areas for improvement and gain valuable insights into OPERAS' current state, empowering OPERAS to identify opportunities for enhancement and growth in UCD and ResearchOps. In this example (Table 4), we present a model adapted from the Pistoia Alliance UXLS Research Ops Framework (2023) that outlines various levels of UX maturity and organises research operations into eight key areas, as proposed by the ResearchOps framework. Adopting this or a similar (modified) approach will enable OPERAS to systematically evaluate its current UX maturity level and pinpoint specific areas requiring further improvement and expansion of the UCD approach and existing UX practice.

Table 4: UX maturity levels to the eight ResearchOps pillars. Source: Pistoia Alliance

Pillar	Category	Activity	UX maturity level	
Environment	Buy in	Start creating buy-in (isolated service and/or project teams)	1. Beginning	
		Peers and management	2. Developing	
		Leadership and stakeholders	3. Integrating	
	Socialising research	Identify platforms for socialising research (already provided, not new)	3. Integrating	
		Reporting value of research (cross-team, cross-project) and driving awareness (yearly reports)	3. Integrating	
	Value of research			
	Define user research protocols for reuse	Identify user research protocol (past projects; reusable components)	2. Developing	
Library of user research protocols and templates (shared user research glossary)		3. Integrating		
Refinement of user research protocols as needed		4. Optimising		

Scope		Continuous improvement and evaluation of user research protocols as a standard process	5. Insights driven
	Sharing of user research insight	Share research insights with smaller project team	2. Developing
		Communication (plan and who to share with?)	3. Integrating
		Templates analysis/briefing/sharing user research insights (designed for different tools, e.g., pptx, Jira)	4. Optimising
	User research process	Define the user research process (when user research should be engaged, stakeholder meetings, kick-off's)	2. Developing
	Guidelines for conducting research	Guiding principles when approaching user research (frameworks, lab guidelines, org policies)	2. Developing
	Research narrative	Connecting research findings with org initiatives and strategy	3. Integrating
		Roadmap of research that has/is being done	4. Optimising
	Measurements and metrics	Implements protocols to measure user research (e.g., SUS, UEQ)	3. Integrating
		Set up a user research measurement framework at individual service/project level (e.g., HEART)	4. Optimising

		Set up an org user-research framework to measure the impact (e.g. KPI, ROI)	5. Insights driven
People	Team roles & responsibilities	No dedicated research	1. Beginning
		Project members (e.g., designer, developers, product owner) doing user research	2. Developing
		Hiring dedicated researchers alongside designers doing research	3. Integrating
		Dedicated research team with specialist research roles (e.g., information architect, services designer)	4. Optimising
		Strategy & innovation research roles and research ops roles and user recruitment roles	5. Insights driven
	Safety aspects	Training for researchers using different tools	2. Developing
	Outside help	Enhance user research capability by hiring outside (e.g., contractor or agency)	2. Developing
	Team building & internal capacities	Research skills and maturity matrix (core team, community); Team structure (centre, hub); Org events dedicated to UX research (incl. PWDR)	3. Integrating
Develop career/professional development progression; executive leadership skills, evolve team structure; strategic user research arm		4. Optimising	

Organisational context	Professional development	Execute a career/professional development progression; executive leader representing UX and user research; strategic user research arm defines research roadmap	5. Insights driven
		Train non-UX practitioners on basic user research skills (workshops, conferences, training)	2. Developing
		User research training; new to UX group; peers review session; peer sharing (club, lunch, community)	3. Integrating
		Secondary opportunities (sharing practitioners between teams)	5. Insights driven
	Physical and virtual infrastructure	Virtual and physical spaces to conduct research (e.g., booking private meeting rooms)	3. Integrating
	Dedicated devices and equipment for conducting research, e.g., eye-trackers, GSR, EEG	4. Optimising	
	Dedicated research space such a usability lab	5. Insights driven	
	Budgeting of user research	Tracking operational spend; balancing in-house vs contractor vs. agency spend; budget allocation per project	4. Optimising
	Justifying costs for user research	Case studies capturing value, capturing metrics such as time on task	3. Integrating
	Persona	Identify and validate user types (personas)	2. Developing

Recruitment & Administration	management	Support adoption of personas across the organisation	3. Integrating
		Create a library of personas understood across the org	4. Optimising
		Digitise continuous feed and updating personas	5. Insights driven
	Keep participants actively engaged	Develop a strategy to keep participants actively engaged in ongoing research	5. Insights driven
		Recruitment strategy	Design a recruitment screener; Define recruitment process
	Build relationship with recruitment agencies; Develop recruiting guidelines (incentives, accessibility, vulnerable)		3. Integrating
	Maintain a diverse participants pool to ensure research momentum		4. Optimising
	Data storage	Storage for raw data e.g. audio/video	1. Beginning
		Establish a culture of sharing	2. Developing
		Develop strategies for cross-sharing of insights	3. Integrating
Continuous improvement of insight sharing (newsletter, library of insights)		4. Optimising	
Automate the sharing of insights as new data added; use prediction algorithms (ML and AI) to push insights to targeted		5. Insights driven	

Data & Knowledge Management		stakeholders	
	Data access audit	Verify who has access to research data	1. Beginning
	Culture of sharing		
	Data governance	Consider FAIR principles when setting up the data infrastructure (data standards that adhere FAIR); Anonymise Personal Identifiable Information (PII)	1. Beginning
		Secure the data and ensure access rights (training, permission)	2. Developing
		Maintain the content (tagging, classifying, metadata); Data guideline and rules; Develop vocabulary for data findability; Implement data retention schedule (store/delete)	3. Integrating
	IP protection	Ensure IP is protected during user research (NDA and Terms & Conditions)	1. Beginning
	Guidelines	Compliance of ethics protocols; Guidelines for issues that may affect UX research	1. Beginning
	Participant consent	Develop a consent form approved by legal team; manage consent (participants able to exit a study)	2. Developing

Governance		Develop a consent library and templates to manage at scale	3. Integrating
	Participant privacy	Remove recording of bystanders; Anonymise identifiable data; Protect identity (pseudonymisation)	2. Developing
		Delete data no longer needed (policy); Distribution policy	3. Integrating
	Code of ethics	Develop a code of ethics for research (ethical standards, non-bias)	3. Integrating
Tools & Infrastructure	Tool management	Identify tools for specific research methods	1. Beginning
		Define a protocol for management of your tools (access, licences, permissions)	2. Developing
		Develop onboarding material for UX practitioners	3. Integrating
	Project planning	Agile research backlog and research planning software	4. Optimising
	Emerging tech for usability testing	Continuously explore new tech for research such as eye tracking, VR	5. Insights driven
	Procurement & IT processes	Consider org procurement & IT process	1. Beginning
	Recruitment tools	Manage research participants using CRM, incentives, consent and scheduling	2. Developing

Insights management	Tools that manage insights generated from user research; 4. Optimising innovative findings based on user research
Defining best practices for different research methodology & techniques	Establish practices to support prioritisation of insights and software to disseminate them 5. Insights driven Establish practices to support prioritisation of insights and software to disseminate them 2. Developing

3. Planning a UCD project

Following a user-centred process cycle is crucial in developing a user-centred system, product, service, or project, regardless of whether the project starts from a problem (e.g. new service) or a challenge related to an existing solution. This cycle includes several stages, starting with a planning phase that involves framing the issue or situation and establishing clear objectives for the task. The planning phase, like the whole UCD process, is characterised by its **iterative nature**, where **divergent thinking** is employed to explore possibilities and gather insights, followed by **convergent thinking** to narrow down and refine options based on stakeholders' input (planning and replanning).

Before applying any UX methods, we must scope any design project appropriately. This process usually starts with the **project brief**, initiated through the OPERAS UCD funnel - initial request or identified situation for study expressed by individuals or organisations stakeholders like OPERAS leadership, project managers/officers, the OPERAS community, end-users, partners and other stakeholders. For EU projects that employ user-centred design methodologies, it's important to note that the scope of the UCD process is, to some extent, defined at the time of project submission.

These diverse stakeholders provide their needs, expectations, and feedback, which influence the creation of the project brief. As the initial request, it expresses interest or emphasises the scenario to be investigated and is crucial in outlining the challenge or intended result for further exploration. Moreover, the project brief may also originate from our own experience or insights, ensuring a comprehensive perspective guiding the project's direction.

Stakeholder consultations via one-on-one **interviews** are often conducted to understand the organisational context and gather initial information about the objectives, target users, and their needs for a specific project. These interviews involve decision-makers and other stakeholders who possess valuable insights into the actual use of the system or service. To streamline the interview process, it is recommended to create a comprehensive list of interview participants, taking into account their diverse backgrounds, including countries, disciplines, career levels, gender, and other relevant factors, and prioritise them based on their expertise and availability of time and resources. A flexible approach is often employed for these interviews, combining guided conversations, informal discussions and semi-structured interviews, which focus on critical themes and last approximately 45 minutes. The interviewer must ensure the anonymity of the interviewees. After the interviews, summarising and utilising the collected data becomes essential for subsequent planning stages.

While in the preparation phase, **observation** is an additional method for gathering valuable insights from stakeholders alongside interviews. This approach entails examining the systems that stakeholders engage with to understand their experiences better. One way to do this is by adopting a non-intrusive stance, quietly observing and documenting participants' activities. A more immersive option involves using participatory observation, where researchers actively interact with the system to understand its operation and effects on users comprehensively. While a solo researcher

can carry out observations, collaborating with team members or having multiple observers can be advantageous for specific projects or seeking a broader perspective. However, it is important to recognise that observation can be resource-intensive, demanding substantial time and resources for effective implementation. To address this challenge, guerrilla observation techniques in users' natural environments can be a valuable alternative. This approach allows us to gather rich contextual information while mitigating some resource constraints commonly associated with traditional observation methods.

After the initial project brief has been approved by the relevant decision-making stakeholders, the next step is to **organise a team** with defined roles and responsibilities for project execution. This team typically includes project managers responsible for scheduling and confirming interviews, storing consent forms, gathering and storing raw and synthesised data, and **liaising** with leadership and relevant stakeholders. Additionally, user researchers or PWDRs are crucial in **selecting research methodologies** for collecting qualitative data, framing the user research plan, conducting interviews, and performing other user research-related activities. The user research chapter contains additional information on various research methodologies.

Dedicated UX teams and researchers supporting innovation

To build a solid foundation for user research and UX within the organisation, we recommend closely connecting the future team (e.g. task force) or even a dedicated user researcher with the Service and Technology Board or the OPERAS Innovation Observatory, which will form a component of the OPERAS-PLUS project. This coordination is expected to facilitate the integration of UX and user research practices into strategic decision-making processes and innovation projects, fostering a user-centric culture and supporting the development of adequate and user-oriented infrastructure and services within open scholarly communication.

After understanding the research objectives, goals, and context from the project brief, we typically create a **user research plan**. It is important to note that the project proposal often includes a general outline of the user research activities and deliverables for funded projects.

The user research plan outlines specific objectives, methodologies, questions, methods, tools, deliverables, activities, timelines, and other logistical aspects, such as participant recruitment criteria. The user research plan also includes user-centred quality objectives as intended outcomes for developing the interactive system, focusing on usability, accessibility, user experience, and avoiding harm during use. The user research plan acts as a roadmap for user research activities, ensuring the research stays focused and aligns with project goals. User Interviews (2022) provides an excellent example and an actionable [template](#) for creating a user research plan, offering practical guidance on structuring and executing user research activities.

In addition to the user research plan, some teams utilise **UCD or UX canvas** as a concise format and visual aid for organising and capturing essential user-centred design aspects. This tool typically features sections for capturing information related to research goals, questions, methods, key insights, and more. The canvas also functions as a high-level summary of the user research plan for communication with stakeholders and team members. Thanks to its flexible format, the UX canvas serves as a valuable tool throughout the research process, helping the team stay focused and quickly adapt to the unique context and requirements of a specific project or organisation.

Figure 10: Example of UX research canvas. Source: Claudia Mascas (https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVM_nC_Vk=/)

User research plans are primarily prepared to guide the following steps: preparing and conducting a strategic event known as the **(stakeholder) kick-off meeting**. This meeting allows stakeholders to meet each other and collect additional information about the project's purpose and its overall context of use from the domain and other experts. Conversations should concentrate on the project's vision, encompassing objectives, challenges, and success criteria, rather than delving into potential solutions regarding functionality or content. Different stakeholders, such as individuals or organisations, have an active interest in an interactive system or service and may be affected by the project's strategic direction or have influence over it. In the context of

OPERAS, all users are stakeholders; however, not all stakeholders are users, as some may not interact with the system/service or use its output. The interests of non-user stakeholders are represented through market/sector requirements and organisational requirements.

This stakeholder meeting aims to foster a shared understanding among participants regarding the diverse matters being discussed. However, achieving this can be challenging due to differing project perspectives among attendees. To promote alignment within the limited time available, it is advisable to incorporate framed activities and utilise tools/techniques that facilitate productive discussions and consensus-building, allowing participants to move beyond repetitive debates and reach a common understanding (for example, use adapted canvases like the Business Model Canvas or UX canvas, prioritise potential target users, create stakeholder maps, and map processes using service blueprints or experience maps for effective strategic alignment in the project). In some cases, dedicated **UX workshops** may further explore and discuss these activities, providing a more focused and in-depth exploration of user experience design and research.

In many user research and UX projects, including representatives of (potential) end-users in the **collaborative planning process** is crucial for aligning with their needs and expectations. Engaging users during this phase yields valuable insights and perspectives that steer the project towards a more user-centric and successful outcome. Involving users allows for a deeper understanding of the context of use and user requirements, helping to shape the project's goals and objectives to meet user expectations and deliver an exceptional user experience.

Central hub and dedicated (data) spaces for projects

To ensure efficient data management throughout the UCD cycle, it is recommended to establish dedicated spaces for the project. This space will serve as a central hub for displaying collected information and providing the necessary resources to progress. It should be user-friendly and engaging for stakeholders while serving as a historical archive of the project's progress. Currently, OPERAS teams and projects use [Confluence](#) as a collaborative and documentation platform, a shared Google Drive for internal document storage and collaboration among team members, [Zenodo](#) as an open-access repository for archiving and sharing research outputs such as publications, datasets, reports, and scholarly materials in a citable and discoverable format, as well as other tools tailored to their specific needs.

Recruitment

Involving target users, often referred to as **participants** during recruitment, in the UX design process is a core principle outlined by the international standard ISO 9241-210 (2019) on user-centred design. Users are crucial in identifying needs, evaluating systems,

and participating in design ideation and generation. In this section, we will shortly present the most critical aspects of participant selection and recruitment, determining the “ideal” number of participants, and strategies to motivate participation. For a more in-depth user overview, refer to the upcoming section 4. User research: context of use and user requirements.

Selecting participants for user research requires acknowledgment that access to all target users might not be feasible. Therefore, researchers usually choose representative users from each identified group to form the study sample, with various sampling methods available to assist in this process.

In some cases, studies may benefit from including users with distinct profiles, such as power users of the target system or service, individuals with specific needs, or non-users. This approach can yield innovative ideas or help differentiate from competitors. However, it's crucial to recognise groups with diverse abilities to ensure equal access and inclusivity. If overlooked, this can lead to serious accessibility issues.

Inclusive participant recruitment

In line with OPERAS' commitment to fostering **positive change in the world**, we prioritise values such as the common good, diversity and inclusion, and democracy. This commitment extends to our participant recruitment process, where we actively seek individuals from diverse geographical regions with proficiency in different languages (**multilingualism**) and representing various cultural norms and customs (**multiculturalism**). We aim to mitigate biases and promote an inclusive research and (co)design process by involving underrepresented groups not only within the scholarly communication chain but also among broader audiences, including individuals engaged in citizen science initiatives and the general public who have an interest in research results.. Through this approach, we gain valuable insights into user experiences and develop solutions that effectively cater to the diverse needs of our users.

The "ideal" number of participants depends on multiple factors like the study's purpose and objectives, whether the aim is to understand or generalise findings, and if the focus is on creating new systems/services or improving existing ones. Time, budget, and chosen research methods (qualitative vs quantitative) also impact this decision, along with the characteristics of target user groups.

Various channels are available for recruiting participants for our studies, such as leveraging our organisation and internal community channels, partnering with other organisations or associations, utilising specialised magazines or journals, leveraging social networks (e.g. OPERAS [Twitter](#) channel or [LinkedIn](#) page), and utilising our personal and professional connections. Additionally, OPERAS partners/members are a valuable source for recruiting users, given their involvement in our initiatives and alignment with our goals and values. In some cases, we also consider engaging specialised recruitment agencies to assist participant recruitment.

While participants' intrinsic motivation and interest in contributing to the research infrastructure for open scholarly communication are precious, it is essential to acknowledge that there may be instances where compensation is necessary due to factors such as time constraints or travel requirements. To incentivise user participation in studies, consider providing non-monetary rewards or customised ones to align with specific participants. Otherwise, it has to be regulated on the organisational level. Typically, prizes are distributed to participants upon the completion of the study.

Secondary research

Before initiating any project, collecting valuable information is essential. Besides involving stakeholders to understand their needs and expectations, the planning phase entails comprehensive data gathering on the project's thematic aspects. This process encompasses problem definition, examination of existing knowledge on the subject, identifying relevant information sources, and evaluation of competitors and their offerings. **Secondary research**, also referred to as desk research or literature review, plays a crucial role in understanding and contextualising the issue. Despite its "secondary" label, we should not underestimate its importance, as it forms an essential part of the process.

When preparing the user research plan, secondary research takes various forms depending on the project's specific aim or the type of system or service being (re)designed. Secondary research includes **academic or scholarly research**, scholarly books, journals, databases, and **statistical research** relying on historical data. **Internal research** leverages existing documents within the organisation to prevent duplication of effort and contribute to previous work. Conversely, **external research** involves benchmarking against documents, projects, or programs outside the organisation, spanning different public, non-profit, academic, and private sectors.

Competitive analysis, a commonly used form of external research, is conducted to gain insights and identify sector trends and developments in relation to the project or service being developed. In UX research, terms like "competitor analysis," "market analysis," and "benchmarking" are often used interchangeably, depending on the specific context and objectives. It's generally recommended to analyse 5 to 10 competitors for a thorough assessment (Komninos 2019). This analysis includes evaluating the content, functionality, and, most importantly, user experience while pinpointing each solution's strengths and weaknesses. The objective is to identify the unique competitive advantages of each product or service. If resources allow, user testing can be integrated into the competitive analysis. The results will be compiled into a report, offering stakeholders valuable insights into the competitive landscape and guiding strategic decisions.

Open access source

We highly recommend using open-access sources for secondary research. Prioritising open-access sources promotes transparency, collaboration, and

knowledge sharing, improving the quality of the user research process in the long run.

Ethics

Before conducting a user study, it is crucial to clearly understand the key ethical and legal principles that must be upheld. As researchers, we treat participants ethically, prioritise their well-being, avoid discrimination, and safeguard both their data and our organisation's. These ethical principles apply to all parties involved, including the research participants, organisers, and the system or service being used. Suppose specific sessions are delegated to other agencies or institutions. In that case, ensuring they are fully aware of the ethical principles and adequately prepared to handle sessions with participants is imperative.

Before starting a study with a participant, it is essential to adhere to the following ethical considerations:

- Obtain free and informed consent from the participant (e.g. [DARIAH ELDAH Consent Form Wizard](#)).
- Communicate the study's objectives to the participant.
- Inform the participant about the recording of sessions, if applicable.
- Explain the personal information that will be collected and how it will be processed.
- Assure the participant of the anonymity and confidentiality of their data.
- Specify the type of incentive provided to the participant.
- Inform the participant about their right to withdraw from the study at any time.
- Discuss any potential risks associated with their participation, even if minimal, in our field.
- Communicate any duties or obligations, mainly if a confidentiality clause (NDA) is involved.
- Provide the name and contact details of a designated person who can address any questions or concerns the participant may have regarding the study or their rights.

During the studies, personal data collection and processing are subject to strict legislation in most countries. The organisation should ensure that it understands and complies with its (national) legal obligations regarding data protection.

User researchers or PWDRs can consult professional codes of conduct, such as those provided by reputable organisations like the User Experience Professionals Association (UXPA 2013), the International Association of User Experience Professionals, or the Interaction Design Association (Code of Conduct - IxDA n.d.). These codes of conduct outline professional ethics and promote an inclusive community that respects diverse

cultures and differences.

Guerrilla mode

Guerrilla methods refer to "discount" usability and UX approaches for identifying user needs or evaluating systems or services (Nielsen 1994). They are characterised by their low cost and minimal effort requirements.

A typical example is conducting a user test within a few minutes at a bar, where randomly selected customers are approached and offered a free coffee in exchange for their participation. It is crucial to note that participants in these scenarios are not strictly "recruited" but rather "approached."

Guerrilla methods can help organisations gradually introduce and showcase the value of UX practices as an effective tool to generate quick buy-ins, actionable insights, and eventual support for broader UX initiatives.

4. User research: context of use and user requirements

This section expands on the fundamental principles and concepts of user-centred design, explicitly understanding the **context of use** (divergent phase) and defining **user requirements** (convergent phase), which have been introduced earlier. The emphasis now moves to examining these concepts through user research. The chapter explores different research methodologies, such as subjective or opinion-based research that collects insights from user perspectives. Additionally, empirical and behaviour-based research approaches will be addressed, focusing on evidence-based studies to guide the design process. Although the chapter cannot provide exhaustive details, it aims to present fundamental concepts and methods related to user research within UCD process.

4.1 Types of user research

Before delving into specific UCD activities during a project's development process, it is good to explore the different types of user research and their related methodologies and approaches. To better understand when to use specific methods, it is helpful to consider a 3-dimensional framework that covers the following aspects, as suggested by Christian Rohrer and Kelley Gordon (2022):

- Attitudinal vs. Behavioural (opinion vs behaviour based),
- Qualitative vs. Quantitative,
- Context of use.

The Attitudinal vs Behavioural Dimension distinguishes between understanding "what people say" and "what people do" (Figure 11). Attitudinal research focuses on people's stated beliefs, measured through surveys, interviews and focus groups, but is limited by people's awareness and willingness to report. On the other hand, behavioural research

examines user behaviour with the system or service, using methods such as contextual inquiry, A/B testing and eye-tracking. Usability and field studies are popular methods combining self-reported and behavioural data, with a suggested emphasis on the behavioural side.

Figure 11: Landscape of user research methods. Source: Christian Rohrer (<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/which-ux-research-methods/>)

The second dimension of user experience research methods differentiates between **qualitative** and **quantitative** studies. Qualitative studies involve observing or interacting with users to collect data on behaviours or attitudes, using methods like interviews, focus groups, participatory design, and contextual inquiry. In contrast, quantitative studies obtain data indirectly through measurements or tools such as surveys or analytics to comprehend behaviours or attitudes. Qualitative methods are particularly well-suited for addressing questions related to the "why" and "how to fix" aspects and providing insights for potential solutions. On the other hand, quantitative methods try to answer questions on quantity, frequency, and magnitude, giving numerical data for "how many" and "how much" questions (Rohrer 2022b).

User research methods can be further categorised beyond the previously mentioned dimensions, including (User interviews 2022):

- **Generative vs evaluative methods** emphasise exploring and creating new ideas and concepts, while evaluative methods evaluate existing designs for feedback and enhancement¹⁴ (sometimes also referred to as formative vs summative evaluation)
- **Remote vs in-person methods** can be performed remotely using online surveys, remote usability testing, interviews, or in-person interaction with researchers and participants.
- **Moderated vs unmoderated methods** involve researcher guidance and engagement during the research session, whereas unmoderated methods enable participants to finish tasks autonomously.

In addition to the previously mentioned user research methods, Hanington and Martin (2019) identify several other types of user research methods, including:

- **Participatory design methods** involve a variety of stakeholders in the design process in order to “co-create, co-operate, and co-design” workshops and similar activities.
- **Observational research methods** involve observing participants in natural settings, for example, field studies and contextual inquiry.
- **Self-reporting research methods** entail gathering data directly from participants, for example, interviews, surveys, questionnaires, and diary studies.
- **Expert-based review methods** are where experts evaluate a system or service based on their knowledge and expertise, focusing on usability and potential improvements, for example, cognitive walkthrough and heuristic evaluation.
- **Design process methods** integrate user research throughout the design process, utilising user personas, user journey mapping, and iterative usability testing to inform and validate design decisions.

Mixed methods approach

The mixed-methods approach combines qualitative and quantitative methods to comprehensively understand complex problems, leveraging the strengths of both approaches for a holistic perspective (Berent-Spillson 2019). Triangulating data from diverse sources enhances information synthesis, enabling a richer analysis and uncovering hidden patterns. This

¹⁴ Hanington and Martin (2019) categorised user research methods, including exploratory, generative, and evaluative methods. Exploratory methods are designed for exploration and gaining deeper insights, while generative methods focus on concept generation, and evaluative methods are used for testing and evaluation.

approach allows researchers to explore different dimensions, gain deeper insights, and effectively tackle complex issues, generating valuable knowledge.

4.2 Context of use

Designing for experience (UX) requires an in-depth understanding of the target users, their actions, and the context in which these actions occur. In UCD, the exploratory phase is vital as it involves thorough research in the relevant domain, identifying challenges, and seeking inspiration. **Empathy** becomes a key element during this phase to collect information, understand users, and delve into their motivations, attitudes, emotions, culture, and past experiences for gaining insights. Traditional empathy maps featuring four quadrants (*Says, Thinks, Does, and Feels*) and a central user or persona are commonly employed to collect this information (Gibbons 2018).

EMPATHY MAP Example (Buying a TV)

Figure 12: Example empathy map. Source: <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/empathy-mapping/>

Information about users can be acquired by listening to what they say and think through interviews, observing what they do via scenarios, usability testing, and customer journey analysis, and finding out about their emotions by directly asking or observing via an emotion recognition system (e.g. facial expression recognition, eye-tracking, galvanic skin response).

This section presents the process of user research, describing and documenting our understanding of the **context of use** in a way that assists the team in progressing the user-centred design process. We undertake this for two primary reasons: a) to facilitate the design, and b) to support the evaluation of the system, product, or service.

Context of use is a “combination of users, goals and tasks, resources, and environment” (ISO 9241-11:2018)

The context of use refers to understanding the users, their activities, problems, and needs. It comprises five components:

- **Users** - “person who interacts with a system, product or service” (ISO 9241-11:2018)
 - All users are considered stakeholders, meaning individuals or organisations with an active interest in an interactive system; however, not all stakeholders are users. It's important to distinguish between primary and secondary users. **Primary users** (direct/indirect) have a specific purpose for using the interactive system, while **secondary users** primarily assist with tasks or maintain the system. In some cases, **indirect users** may use the system through tasks directly performed by secondary users.
 - For later design and evaluation phases, it is essential to document key elements such as demographics (e.g. age, gender, education), psychological and social characteristics (e.g. cognitive abilities, cultural aspects), background information (e.g. language, literacy, knowledge and skills, motivation, attitude), and physical and sensory characteristics (e.g. visual and auditory abilities)
- **Goals** - “intended outcome” of the task (ISO 9241-11:2018)
 - Goals articulate the desired outcomes that users aim to accomplish while performing tasks with an interactive system.
 - For later design and evaluation phases, it is essential to document the goals and responsibilities of user groups and the organisation, intended outcomes and personal goals of individuals within each stakeholder group, and recognise the goals of the organisation itself, as opposed to the users
- **Tasks** - “set of activities undertaken in order to achieve a specific goal” (ISO 9241-11:2018)
 - A task can be broken down into subtasks (e.g. register, login, etc.): the

individual steps required to complete the task, i.e. to achieve the goals.

- For later design and evaluation phases, it is essential to document the description of each task and subtask, as well as the duration, frequency, and complexity associated with each task
- **Environments** - “technical, physical, social, cultural and organisational environments” in which a user interacts with a system, product or service (ISO 9241-11:2018)
 - Physical conditions encompass measurable aspects, such as room size, luminance, and noise; technical conditions involve internet connectivity, power sockets or phone lines, while social conditions encompass factors influenced by society, including work environments, laws and regulations, information access, and interpersonal relationships.
 - For later design and evaluation phases, it is essential to document important factors from the technical environment (tools, equipment, hardware configuration, input devices, network connections, and assistive technologies), socio-cultural and organisational environment (other people, roles and relationships, organisational structure, language, regulations, cultural/work norms and values, privacy, availability of assistance, responsibilities, group dynamics, time pressures, and interruptions), and physical environment (time, location, workplace, lighting, and temperature)
- **Resources** - all means “in attempting to achieve a goal” in the context of use (ISO 9241-11:2018)
 - Resources can be either reusable, including items like laptops, software, and data, or exhaustible, such as time, energy, human effort, finances, and physical materials.

Example:

Interactive system “Online journal platform”

- Context of use: Researchers in social sciences and humanities use mobile devices during their train commutes to access an online journal, read papers, and make annotations for ongoing work.
 - User: Researchers
 - Goal: Make annotations and continue work at home or office
 - Task: Read and highlight important sections, add personal annotations or comments.
 - Environment, social condition: Research group (colleagues)
 - Environment, organisational condition: Public university
 - Environment, cultural condition: Annual research assessment

- Environment, physical condition: Train
- Environment, technical condition: Internet connection
- Resource: Mobile device (phone or tablet); annotation tool (app or paper/pencil)

User researchers employ observation, contextual interviews, focus groups, and user surveys to determine the context of use and create a detailed description. This multifaceted approach provides rich qualitative and quantitative data to inform the UCD process and to make the “**context of use description**” the basis for identifying user needs and tracing them back to their sources. Typically, the context of use description includes these following elements or deliverables:

- **User group profiles**

- generalised descriptions of specific user segments, highlighting their shared characteristics and contexts of use
- Example:
 - Early Career Researchers (ECRs) are a specific user group consisting of individuals pursuing or having recently completed their doctoral studies, typically not older than 40 years. This user group excludes researchers who have already obtained established or tenured positions within their respective fields.
 - Early Career Researchers (ECRs) are characterised by their limited experience in research, often needing more significant exposure to the publication process. Many ECRs express reluctance to publish their work in diamond open-access journals due to concerns raised by their mentors regarding potential exposure to unprofessional or unethical editorial practices that could jeopardise their academic careers.
 - ECRs need help with a dilemma as they receive numerous emails inviting them to publish their papers in various journals. While they are hesitant to respond to these invitations due to concerns about the credibility and legitimacy of the journals, they also experience institutional pressure to adhere to the "publish or perish" culture prevalent in academia.

- **Personas**

- detailed descriptions of fictitious yet realistic users, known as user archetypes, are created using data primarily gathered from interviews and identifying common patterns; valuable tools that promote empathy among designers, empowering them to understand user needs, motivations, and behaviours and effectively address them.
- Example: see, Figure 13: Example of a non-academic persona created for

GoTriple platform (source: Dumouchel et al. 2020)

Mr David Green
 AGE: 48
 POSITION: CEO of a small business
 NATIONALITY: British

USER STORY: As the CEO of a small business I want to find accessible information and collaborate with academics to ensure that our interventions reflect the latest research evidence

NARRATIVE: David is the CEO of a small business working to provide activities supporting positive mental health. He has a specific interest in working with young people and addressing their needs, which are currently not met sufficiently well. He is keen to get an up to date picture of current research recommendations in order to provide direction for his efforts at a practical level. David is very pro-active and would like to collaborate with researchers on a new project. He saw a recent funding call and would very much like to join forces with academics and submit a bid. David is both time and money pressured, and cannot afford to pay to access research publications. As he isn't affiliated with a University, many of the publications that he finds when he does a Google search are not available for free. He would prefer to be shown only open-source material, but isn't sure how to go about this. He often looks for information on populations, such as data on poverty across geographical regions. He is usually looking at deficits, where things aren't going well, trends in education, health, social mobility, the many things that have an impact on mental health. He feels that searching for information can be a real scattergun approach unless he knows the exact key words to use, but often the data he needs is quite hidden. Sometimes he's looking for narratives, sometimes for quantitative information. David finds that some academic work is just not accessible, he feels as though it should be useful, but he just doesn't understand it, it's not written in terms that a lay person might find it very useful, he questions who the audience is for this work. David tends to use Twitter a lot to see what new initiatives that are coming through, what recent reports have been written and for new deadlines that are coming through. He thinks Twitter is a brilliant source of fresh information, but is a bit frustrated that you have to be on it a lot or you lose the information in the feed.

PAIN POINTS:

- Lack of access to academic research (that is not open source) due to lack of University affiliation and a tight budget
- Inaccessible research publications
- Finding datasets with up-to-date statistics around mental health

GOALS:

- Finding who key researchers and players are in the field
- Getting accessible summaries of the research quickly
- Making contact with academics to investigate collaboration for a research proposal

QUOTE: "As an organisation we've made it part of our distinctiveness that we really care about research, we want people to know that what we do is founded in good quality research and good quality knowledge and understanding. As what we do is so practice based, we're taking all of that theory and stuff that's gone before and saying 'this is how it applies here'."

TECH EXPERTISE: ██████████
ENGAGEMENT RESEARCH: ██████████
COLLABORATION: ██████████

Tools Used: Twitter; MS Office; Google; YouTube

The TRIPLE project is funded by the European Commission, under Grant Agreement No. 863420

Figure 13: Example of a non-academic persona created for the GoTriple platform. Source: Dumouchel et al. 2020

● **As-is scenarios**

- narrative descriptions that illustrate how users currently complete tasks within their specific environments, bringing the user's journey to life and highlighting pain points, opportunities, and potential areas of improvement.
- Example: see, Figure 14: Example of a non-academic as-is scenario created for GoTriple platform (source: Dumouchel et al. 2020)

Figure 14: Example of a non-academic scenario for the GoTriple platform. Source: Dumouchel et al. 2020

- **Task models**

- break down complex tasks into smaller subtasks, providing a systematic approach that allows UX professionals and stakeholders to gain clarity, understand the user's path, and identify areas for optimization by examining the steps users need to take to accomplish their goals (often represented by prototypes, but in our case, we will provide an example based on explicit documentation)
- Example:
 - **Interactive System:** A discovery platform for open scholarly publications
 - **User Group:** Researcher from Croatia
 - **Goal:** Find open-access publications published within EU-funded projects with author affiliation from Croatia to gather information for a report on OA publishing practices within EU-funded projects.
 - **The situation that triggers the task** (contextual precondition): The user is writing a report as part of a project deliverable related to OA publishing practices within EU-funded projects.

- **Task:** Find all relevant publications to achieve the set goal.
- **Reason for starting the task:** To gather information on open-access publications with author affiliation from Croatia in the context of EU-funded projects for the report.
- **Subtasks:**
 - Identify appropriate search keywords and criteria for EU-funded projects and author affiliation from Croatia.
 - Access the interactive discovery platform for open scholarly publications.
 - Conduct a search using the identified keywords and other criteria.
 - Filter the search results to include only publications related to EU-funded projects.
 - Filter the search results to include only publications with author affiliation from Croatia.
 - Review the search results and examine each publication's details and metadata.
 - Assess the relevance of each publication based on the defined criteria.
 - Save the relevant publications for further analysis and inclusion in the report.
 - Repeat the search and filtering process to ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant publications.
 - Document the findings and compile them into a comprehensive list or report for the project deliverable on OA publishing practices within EU-funded projects.
- **User journey maps**
 - Visually represent the touchpoints where users interact with the interactive system and organisation, providing a holistic view of the user experience and highlighting opportunities for improving satisfaction and engagement.
 - Example: Figure 15: Example user journey map of an experienced Wikipedia editor and translator (source: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Experienced_Translator_Journey_Map.png)

Figure 15: Example user journey map. Source: Wikimedia

- **User story maps** differ from a user journey map in that it primarily aims to organise development activity rather than to depict the users' recent experience.
 - Example: Figure 16: Example story map from OPERAS Vera project (source: William J. Costello)

Figure 16: Example story map from the OPERAS Vera project. Source: William J. Costello

4.3 User requirements

After a comprehensive understanding of the context of use, prioritisation and focus become crucial. In the UCD process, the subsequent step entails identifying **user needs** and **requirements**, serving as the foundation for designing and evaluating a system or service that fulfils those needs. Hick's law underscores the relationship between decision-making time and the number of choices, emphasising the importance of simplifying a system's user interface to enhance its usability potential. Optimisation of the interface should specifically target users' frequently performed tasks that yield valuable outcomes.

The term "user needs" is frequently used broadly, encompassing the functionality users require and essentially serving as a synonym for "user requirements." However, in this framework, we apply a more precise definition where user needs represent the essential prerequisites for users to achieve their goals within a specific context of use. Identifying these needs is vital for converting contextual information into clear and valid user requirements, independent of any suggested solution. Methods such as interviews, observations, user surveys, usability evaluations, and expert analysis help derive these user needs. We can consider user needs as gaps between the current and desired states. Example of a user need expressed in "user story format":

- As part of an institutional annual research assessment with a specified deadline for submitting a report (*context of use*), an employee from the linguistics department (*user*) needs to gather the metrics for published book usage (*prerequisite*) to fill in the requested data and submit the report on time (*goal*).

The simplicity and precision of this format are precious as they encourage clear thinking about the user's identity and desired goals. Effective user-need descriptions should be framed in language that reflects the users' perspectives and avoids technical jargon. It is crucial for a user need description to focus on the user and their objectives rather than on the system itself.

The discovered user needs are the foundation for establishing user requirements that guide the design and assessment of the system or service, ensuring a user-centred approach throughout the development process.

User requirement is a "condition or capability that must be met or possessed by a system, system component, product, or service to satisfy an agreement, standard, specification, or other formally imposed documents" (ISO 9241-11:2018), and user requirements are special requirements that provide the "basis for the design and evaluation of interactive systems to meet the user needs" (ISO 9241-210:2019)

User requirements stem from user needs and can be directly derived from the context of use description in simple systems (Table 5). These requirements, which can be qualitative or quantitative, serve as the basis for designing and evaluating interactive systems. The precise formulation of user requirements helps resolve potential disputes

between involved parties. Qualitative requirements focus on system usage, while quantitative requirements set measurable goals for user-centred quality. These requirements are evaluated and refined using (low-fidelity) prototype testing with users. Here is an example of a user need and corresponding user requirement:

Table 5: Example of a user need and corresponding user requirement

User need	User requirement
Example:	Examples:
<p>User need: As part of an institutional annual research assessment with a specified deadline for submitting a report, an employee from the linguistics department needs to gather the metrics for published book usage to fill in the requested data and submit the report on time.</p>	<p>User Requirement 1: The institutional publishing platform shall provide access to comprehensive metrics for book usage, including the number of times each book has been accessed and relevant usage statistics.</p> <p>User Requirement 2: The institutional publishing platform shall allow the employee to easily export and download the book usage metrics in a suitable format for inclusion in the annual research assessment report.</p> <p>User Requirement 3: The institutional publishing platform shall provide visual representations or graphical charts of the book usage metrics to facilitate the employee's understanding and interpretation of the data, aiding in preparing a comprehensive and visually appealing annual research assessment report.</p> <p>Qualitative user requirement: The institutional publishing platform shall provide a user-friendly interface that allows users to select their preferred search criteria for gathering book usage metrics.</p>

Quantitative user requirement: The institutional publishing platform shall achieve a user satisfaction rate of at least 80%, where users who have completed the export of usage metrics are required to respond with "Agree" or "Strongly agree" to the statement that the system was easy to use.

In addition to user requirements, projects should also consider other factors and differentiate between various types of requirements, such as market, organisational, and technical requirements. These aspects are essential for a thorough understanding of the project's scope and objectives, although they may fall beyond the scope of this framework.

After completing the previous steps in the research phase, the team proceeds to synthesise the gathered research results. This involves analysing and interpreting the collected data to identify patterns and themes across the research findings. The synthesis process helps align the research results with the project brief and user research plan, enabling the team to uncover valuable insights. These insights, viewed through the lens of user-centred design, reveal opportunities in the form of "touchpoints, root issues, important moments, best practices, pain points, or end-to-end experience mapping" (Human-Centered Design: Discovery Stage Field Guide 2019).

Before advancing to the next phase of the UCD process, the final step effectively communicates the results from the previous two stages to key stakeholders. The presentation should engage the audience and be concise, supported by photos, visualisations, and quotes that enhance the UCD storytelling approach. The goal is to initiate a broader discussion that leads to consensus among the stakeholders. The design phase can commence once the key results have been presented and an agreement is reached. However, if consensus is not achieved, it is necessary to backtrack one or two steps, reframe the approach, and initiate a second research round. The iterative nature of the UCD process allows for early identification of any issues or challenges, ensuring that time and resources are not invested in a flawed design.

5. Design solutions

According to ISO 9241-210 (2019), the design phase involves transforming user requirements into physical or digital representations of the interactive system based on the analysis of the context of use and the deliverables generated during that phase (such as user group descriptions, as-is scenarios, personas, user journey maps, and task models). These representations can range from simple paper sketches to fully interactive simulations. Throughout the design process, considerations are given to principles of user-system interaction, heuristics, user interface guidelines, visual style guides, user mental models, design patterns, and other elements that enhance the overall user experience. The solutions created during different design stages evolve and increase in

fidelity. Often, multiple alternatives are combined to capture the best elements and effectively address identified needs. The design phase is **iterative** and incorporates several **user-centred evaluation** stages to gather feedback and improve the solution (as discussed in the Evaluation section). The generative and evaluative methods work together in cycles in the design phase.

5.1 Principles for UI design

Designing for user experience is an innovative process that considers user satisfaction (emotional and aesthetic aspects), effectiveness, and efficiency. While it requires creativity, there are fundamental **interaction principles** (as outlined in ISO 9241-110) that serve as a baseline:

- suitability for the task
- self-descriptiveness
- conformity with user expectations
- suitability for learning
- controllability
- error tolerance
- suitability for individualisation

User engagement

"The interactive system presents functions and information in an inviting and motivating manner supporting continued interaction with the system" (ISO 9241-110 2020).

User engagement plays a significant role in shaping a positive user experience, requiring a careful balance to avoid negative consequences. Ethical considerations should drive the implementation of engagement techniques, as not all approaches are appropriate for every interactive system. Adhering to the six interaction principles is a prerequisite for user engagement, ensuring the system is suitable and descriptive, conforms to expectations, facilitates learning, provides control, and avoids errors.

In addition to the interaction principles outlined in ISO 9241-110, other well-recognised **usability heuristics**, such as Jakob Nielsen's (2020) ten usability heuristics (e.g. visibility of system status, user control and freedom, consistency and standards, help & documentation, etc.), can help teams achieve the desired level of usability.

5.2 UI prototyping

During the initial design stage, UX teams or PWDRs focus on transforming user

requirements into tangible representations such as use scenarios, storyboards, user journey maps, and task models. These deliverables describe or visualise how tasks can be accomplished using the intended system or service. **Use scenarios** are narrative descriptions in text format that outline the steps and actions users will take to complete specific tasks. On the other hand, **storyboards** consist of visual frames similar to comic books that illustrate the user-system interaction. **Task models** or **user journey maps**, which were developed during the analysis of the context of use, are refined and updated during the early design phase to provide a clear understanding of user interactions and workflows.

The subsequent stage in the design process involves creating **prototypes** that illustrate different design representations based on the opportunities identified in previous steps. A prototype serves as a representation of some or all aspects of a system or service. It can range from simple paper sketches to highly interactive simulations that closely resemble the final solution in appearance and behaviour. The main objective of a prototype is to facilitate **usability evaluations**, often through **usability testing**. The insights gained from these evaluations inform the iterative redesign and refinement of the prototype. Additionally, prototypes give stakeholders and users an early impression of the interactive system's design, fostering productive discussions and feedback.

Prototypes play a crucial role in the design process and can be categorised as low-fidelity or high-fidelity, depending on the level of detail and interaction they offer. **Low-fidelity prototypes** are often created based on use scenarios and storyboards. They are cost-effective and easily disposable if they prove ineffective. Examples of low-fidelity prototypes include **wireframes**, which consist of basic shapes, placeholder text, minimal visual elements, and **paper-based sketches** (Figure 17).

4

Homepage

Fabrice

1. Interface to bulk our personal project session	2. To enter in my session	3. Shared proactive destination... manage face to a difficulty in daily life.	4. definition of the project and skills	5. Facilities for large scale communication/collaboration
6. Working easy, time not wasted	7. easy organization for the team	8. easy communication in the team?	9. easy dissemination to citizens	10. all Social Network

11. not the same thing as number 9?

Susana

1. I assume this is about tools that can be used to manage projects - difficult to understand. If I already have a tool, why do I need to include it here	2. Easy way to contact with your team; it seems a very useful tool. :-)	3. Place to create/ put any project you have in order to be able to share it others; not sure about the "master" word, if it is the best word. :-)	4. Where you can assign the roles of the different partners you need on the project	5. First phrase not very clear to me - why the "past the technical jargon"? It is a relevant question, but not work to be good to have it here
6. Means that you can share information you have in the platform using these tools (not sure about the other way around - if you can easily integrate something you have on the tools on VERA.	7. I imagine if you judge the information in the platform, you will have access to a network of people that is associated with VERA	8. Not sure what I can get from this - is this for my team to know/learn?	9. I imagine if you judge the information in the platform, you will have access to a network of people that is associated with VERA	10. Means that you can share information you have in the platform using these tools (not sure about the other way around - if you can easily integrate something you have on the tools on VERA.

The wireframe shows the homepage layout for VERA. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Projects', 'About', 'Other', 'Create project', and 'Log in'. A main header section contains the text 'Collaborate smarter to face societal challenges together' and 'Collaborate with others easily, engage in discussion and share results to make a real impact in the community.' Below this is a 'Create Project' button. A section titled 'VERA Helps' contains three columns of text and images, each with a numbered annotation (4, 5, 6). The first column discusses starting a citizen science project, the second about engaging with like-minded people, and the third about bringing tools together. A 'The VERA Advantage' section follows, with three numbered annotations (7, 8, 9) pointing to specific features: 'Synchronize Your Team', 'Work Together', and 'Connect with the Public'. A sidebar on the right contains a 'In general, good second sentence helps explain better' note.

Figure 17: Example wireframe from the OPERAS Vera project. Source: William J. Costello

During a usability evaluation, low-fidelity prototypes can be tested with participants who replace the "machine" by manually interacting with the prototype. Through an iterative process, low-fidelity prototypes are gradually refined into **high-fidelity prototypes**. These high-fidelity prototypes, for example, **interactive mock-ups** or **fully functioning prototypes**, are the foundation for developing a fully functional interactive system that meets user requirements. Once the high-fidelity prototype meets the necessary criteria, it can be further developed and released to users.

In the design process, the development of **information architecture** and **navigation structure** goes hand in hand with creating prototypes. From a user-centred perspective, information architecture involves the naming and organisation of information that needs to be accessible to users. It focuses on structuring and presenting information to facilitate user understanding and navigation. Similarly, the navigation structure encompasses the user interface's logical arrangement of screens, pages, and windows. It includes the links and menus that enable users to navigate between different sets of information. The goal is to create a coherent and intuitive system that allows users to find and access the information they need easily.

Card sorting is a commonly used method for creating and evaluating a user-centred navigation structure. This method involves participants organising information into categories or groups based on their **mental models** and expectations. By observing how users categorise and relate information, designers can refine the navigation structure to better align with user preferences and needs (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Example of a card sorting session. Source: Yandle (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/yandle/907929818/sizes/l/in/photostream/>)

The outcome of the previous design activity is a comprehensive **user interface specification** that serves as a detailed blueprint resulting from the UCD process. This specification is essential for developers as it provides the necessary information to implement the interactive system effectively.

Communication of design solutions and seeking consensus

Before moving to the implementation (deliver) phase, **communicating** the proposed solutions and **seeking consensus** with relevant stakeholders, including project members, development teams, and other involved parties is crucial. It helps minimise misunderstandings, mitigate risks, and increase the chances of successful project outcomes. Additionally, consensus-building fosters a sense of ownership and

collaboration among stakeholders, creating a supportive environment for the design process.

5.3 UI guidelines

During this phase, the design team creates **user interface guidelines**, which consist of specific rules and recommendations for designing and implementing the user interface. These guidelines cover various aspects, such as the appearance of user interface elements, typography, colour schemes, error messaging, and more. They ensure consistency and cohesiveness across the interface and contribute to a seamless user experience.

User interface guidelines are often consolidated into a **style guide**, which defines the overall visual and behavioural standards for the user interface across systems and services developed by the same organisation. Style guides play an important role in designing for user experience as they ensure a consistent and unified experience throughout the usage (Figure 19). Additionally, **design patterns** are included within style guides as standard solutions for recurring design challenges. These design patterns offer proven approaches to address specific usability or user experience issues, such as pop-ups providing additional information, wizards for onboarding new users, and FAQs for addressing common questions and concerns.

Figure 19: Example user interface style guide by Material. Source: <https://m2.material.io>

6. Evaluating the design

The evaluation phase is critical in the iterative, UCD process. It entails testing the solutions devised during the design phase against user requirements. By collecting feedback from target users or experts, the quality of these solutions is evaluated and validated, or suggestions for enhancements are made.

During the evaluation phase, users engage with the mock-ups or prototypes developed in the design phase, enabling the testing and refinement of solutions. The resulting recommendations guide the development of new and improved solutions. The iterative cycle continues until the system achieves the anticipated level of quality, that is, aligning with user requirements as well as relevant interaction principles, heuristics, and user interface guidelines. This leads to creating the final product, which can be implemented and launched.¹⁵

Usability and user experience assessment, which may occur at any time during the UCD process, from the early discovery phase to delivery and beyond, can be carried out using various user-centred evaluation methods and approaches, as outlined in ISO 9241-210

¹⁵ In real-world projects, various constraints, such as time, budget, and technical limitations, need to be considered and balanced throughout the iterative process.

(2019). While usability inspection and usability testing are commonly used to evaluate the usability of a system, their focus is primarily on objective measures of effectiveness and efficiency. However, user experience encompasses a broader range of subjective factors, including emotions, satisfaction, and overall impression. Therefore, in this section, we will present only the four most common approaches, according to the ISO family of 9241 standards, for assessing user experience:

1. **Usability tests** or user-based testing
2. **Usability inspections** or inspection-based evaluation
3. **User surveys** and **usability/UX scales**
4. **Long-term monitoring**

Part B of this framework presents additional evaluation methods and tools for UCD and UX.

Building OPERAS research methods bank

The list of methods provided in **Part B** is an ongoing effort and is incomplete, as numerous other methods are available. Part B is the initial step towards developing the OPERAS research methods bank, which will be integrated into the shared Confluence workspace. We aim to regularly update the list with new insights and enhance the descriptions of the most widely used methods. It's important to note that all methods can be customised, combined, and adjusted to suit the specific needs of each project or service.

6.1 Usability tests

Usability testing focuses on observing representative users performing specific tasks to assess their ability to interact with an interactive system. It is not principally aimed at gathering personal opinions or engaging in discussions with users.

The usability testing process typically consists of three phases:

1. **Planning:** This involves creating a usability test guide and recruiting suitable participants for the test.
2. **Conducting the test sessions:** The usability test is carried out with participants, guided by the prepared usability test guide.
3. **Writing the usability test report and communicating findings:** The usability test results are documented in a usability test report.

To prepare for the usability test:

- Write a comprehensive usability test guide that includes all necessary information.
- Define specific usability test tasks that participants will need to perform and

prepare any necessary prototypes or wireframes to test.

- Recruit appropriate participants for the test.

The **usability test guide** serves as a reference for the moderator during the test session. It usually includes:

- A checklist for pre-test preparations.
- Topics to cover during the briefing.
- Interview questions to ask before the test.
- Usability test tasks.
- Interview questions for post-test discussions.

During the **usability test session**, the moderator is responsible for conducting the test while other team members take notes. Whether onsite or remote, observers may also be present to observe the session.

Usability test tasks are specific instructions given to participants during a usability test to assess their interaction with the system. Here are two sample tasks for the usability testing of a peer-reviewed academic journal reviewer using a journal management system:

1. **Task 1 (Reviewing a manuscript):** Imagine you have been assigned to review a manuscript. Find the section on the journal management system where you can access the assigned manuscript, read it thoroughly, and provide your feedback.
2. **Task 2 (Checking reviewer deadlines):** As a reviewer, you must stay on top of your assigned tasks. Find the section or page on the journal management system that displays your upcoming deadlines and review due dates. Check if the system provides clear and easily accessible information about these deadlines.

Recruiting is crucial in selecting suitable participants for UCD activities such as focus groups, contextual interviews, or usability tests. A recruitment screener assesses whether candidates possess the necessary characteristics to participate in the activity. These characteristics are typically derived from personas and user group profiles, considering personal and professional background, subject matter knowledge, attitudes, and interests.

During the usability test sessions, several steps are involved:

1. **Briefing:** The usability test participant is provided with information about the purpose of the test and their role in it. This helps set the context and expectations for the session.
2. **Pre-test interview:** A pre-test interview is conducted before starting the usability test tasks. This interview asks participants about their background, previous experience with the system or service, or any relevant information. This helps gather insights into their prior knowledge and expectations.
3. **Usability test tasks:** The participant is then given specific tasks using the

interactive system. These tasks are designed to assess the usability of the system and its ability to meet user needs. The moderator observes the participant's interactions and notes any issues or challenges.

4. **Post-test interview:** After completing the usability test tasks, a post-test interview occurs. This interview focuses on the participant's overall user experience, impressions of the system, and any feedback they may have. This provides valuable insights into their satisfaction, preferences, and suggestions for improvement.

By following these steps, the usability test session effectively evaluates the interactive system's usability and gathers valuable participant feedback.

The final step in the usability testing process is to write the usability test report and timely **communicate** the findings to relevant stakeholders or team members. The report typically includes an executive summary, a comprehensive collection of usability findings (including positive ones), relevant screenshots or images, user characteristics and selection criteria, and the usability test guide. Producing a usability test report is essential, even if resources are limited. A basic report can consist of 3-5 pages or slides, covering the executive summary, key findings, and the list of usability test tasks.

Usability findings can encompass both **usability problems** and **positive findings**. Reporting positive findings is important to ensure that teams know aspects of the interactive system that work well and should be kept the same. It also promotes a positive attitude towards the usability test report and the overall evaluation. Usability findings are often rated to indicate their impact, criticality, and consequences on usability (e.g., minor, serious, catastrophic). These ratings assist teams in prioritising the order in which usability problems should be addressed. **Ratings** are typically based on the perspective of the usability test participants and may involve collaboration with a domain expert.

6.2 Usability inspections

Usability inspection methods involve evaluators assessing an interactive system to identify potential usability problems and deviations from user requirements and established principles. These principles can include interaction principles, heuristics, and user interface guidelines. Typically, usability inspection is conducted by UX professionals or subject matter experts who draw upon their prior experience with usability issues and their knowledge of user interface guidelines and style guides.

A well-known form of usability inspection is heuristic evaluation, introduced by Nielsen in 1994 (2020). It involves systematically examining the user interface to evaluate its compliance with generally applicable principles or heuristics of usable design.

Nielsen's usability heuristics include the following:

1. Visibility of system status.
2. Match between system and the real world.
3. User control and freedom.

4. Consistency and standards.
5. Help users recognise, diagnose and recover from errors.
6. Error prevention.
7. Recognition rather than recall.
8. Flexibility and efficiency of use.
9. Aesthetic and minimalist design.
10. Help and documentation.

Various usability researchers have proposed guideline lists for heuristic evaluations. For example, Ben Shneiderman et al. (2018) defines eight "golden rules" of user interface design.¹⁶

Accessibility Guidelines for Usability Inspection

The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 (2018), created by W3C's Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI), offer recommendations to enhance accessibility in web-based interactive systems. These guidelines cater to individuals with disabilities, accommodating visual, auditory, motor, and cognitive impairments while enhancing overall usability.

WCAG-WAI guidelines serve as a valuable resource for assessing accessibility, featuring testable success criteria sorted into three conformance levels: A (lowest), AA, and AAA (highest). They are based on four principles:

1. Perceivable: Ensuring content and controls can be accessed according to users' needs.
2. Operable: Facilitating navigation and interaction using various input devices.
3. Understandable: Present clear and comprehensible information to support user interpretation.
4. Robust: Coding content for compatibility and accessibility across different software and assistive technologies.

6.3 User surveys and standardised questionnaires

User surveys are valuable for collecting data by soliciting users' factual information and opinions through questionnaires. These surveys can serve multiple purposes, such as measuring satisfaction and user experience and gaining insights into the context of use (Marsh 2022).

When measuring satisfaction or user experience, user surveys often utilise closed-ended

¹⁶ Those who don't own the book can find the eight golden rules in the following source (Wong, 2020).

questions. For instance, respondents may be asked to rate statements on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 indicating "strongly disagree," 3 representing "neutral," and 5 reflecting "strongly agree." Here are some examples of satisfaction evaluation questions related to the new GoTriple platform:

- How would you rate the new GoTriple platform's visual appeal? (Scale: 1-5)
- How easy is it to navigate and use the new GoTriple platform? (Scale: 1-5)
- How effectively does the new GoTriple platform allow you to find publications quickly? (Scale: 1-5)
- To what extent does the new GoTriple platform meet your expectations? (Scale: 1-5)

A substantial number of survey responses (hundreds or more) are typically required to ensure statistical reliability. Additionally, it is crucial to conduct testing during the development phase of user surveys to ensure that the questions are easily understood by the intended respondents and accurately capture their perspectives.

Standardised questionnaires have gained popularity as a user experience research method for collecting self-reported metrics and quantifying users' subjective impressions of a system, product, or service.¹⁷ These questionnaires consist of predetermined questions or statements that follow specific measurement procedures. They are designed to be used repeatedly across various domains. To be considered standardised, these questionnaires undergo psychometric validation during their development stage, ensuring reliability, validity, and sensitivity (Sauro & Lewis, 2016). They can be employed in formative evaluation during product development and testing and in summative evaluation for final product design or redesign.

One widely used standardised questionnaire is the **Net Promoter Score (NPS)**, which measures customer loyalty or satisfaction using a single-item question:

- *How likely would you recommend our company/product/service to a friend or colleague?*
 - *Not at all likely* ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ *Extremely likely*

The most common format for items in UX questionnaires involves short statements describing an aspect of interaction with a product or a product design feature. Participants rate their agreement or disagreement with the statement on an answer scale. For example, an item from the **System Usability Scale (SUS)** is:

- *I think that I would like to use this system frequently.*
 - *Strongly disagree* ○ ○ ○ ○ *Strongly agree*

In the **User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)**, participants express their impression of

¹⁷ A wide range of questionnaires and assessment tools are available in user experience research, each with its distinct approach and purpose. Examples include SUS, QUIS, PSSUQ, SUMI, CSUQ, WAMMI, AttrakDiff2, UEQ, UMUX, VisAWI, meCUE, SUPR_Q, and others.

the product on a semantic dimension using a pair of adjectives with opposite meaning, e.g.:

- *Attractive* o o o o o o *Unattractive*

While it is not feasible to include an exhaustive list of all available UX questionnaires within this framework, we encourage consulting relevant sources, such as Martin Schrepp's (2021) book on UX questionnaires, for further information.

6.4 Long-term monitoring

“A human-centred design process should also include **long-term monitoring** of the use of the product, system or service. This involves collecting user input in different ways over a period of time.” (ISO 9241-210 2019)

Follow-up evaluation is an integral part of system evaluation and typically occurs within a specified timeframe, such as six months to a year after system launch. It focuses on assessing system performance and collecting data to determine if user needs and requirements have been met accurately (ISO 9241-210 2019).

It is essential to distinguish between **short-term evaluation** and **long-term monitoring**. Some effects of using an interactive product, system, or service may only become apparent after an extended period of use. Additionally, external factors such as unexpected legislation changes can also impact. While immediate action may not be necessary, the gathered information can be valuable for future modifications or developments of the product, system, or service (ISO 9241-210 2019).

Long-term monitoring and follow-up evaluation require various approaches and methods to assess system performance and collect relevant data. These methods should be selected and combined based on specific objectives, available resources, and the evaluation's context. Here are some examples of these methods:

- Longitudinal studies: Track user experience, performance, and satisfaction over a longer time.
- Usage analytics: Uncover long-term patterns and areas for improvement.
- Surveys and interviews: Gather feedback on evolving needs and changes in satisfaction.
- Observational studies: Observe long-term usage patterns, behaviours, and challenges.
- Support and Feedback Channels: Identify potential long-term issues and emerging needs.
- Comparative studies: Evaluate the impact of modifications on user experience and performance.

Expert evaluations: Gain external perspective on usability and suggested improvements.

7. Conclusions and next steps

This deliverable serves as the initial document for Task 6.2, which focuses on developing a common methodological framework for achieving user-centred quality objectives of OPERAS services. It provides a detailed description of the framework, emphasising its value as a methodological resource for designing successful user-centred projects and services within OPERAS. The framework aligns with OPERAS' core values of open scholarly communication, diversity, and inclusion, empowering users and offering them a seat in decision-making processes for service creation. By supporting UX research and UCD, the UCQ-FRAME provides processes, methods/tools, deliverables, and practices that enhance user engagement in open scholarly communication and publishing.

Part A of the framework establishes foundational concepts, principles, and methods to guide user-centred design processes and integrate user experience research and design in projects. Following the ISO 9241 series of standards and incorporating the ResearchOps framework, the framework outlines an iterative design cycle with tailored methods and tools. This integration establishes standardised processes and enables systematic evaluation of user experience maturity. In addition to emphasising the need for dedicated UX teams, data collection spaces, and inclusive participant recruitment, the design cycle highlights the importance of conducting comprehensive research on the context of use and user requirements. The process progresses through the design phase, aligned with user-system interaction principles, and concludes with the evaluation phase involving feedback collection and enhancements. By following the guidance in Part A, OPERAS can enhance UCD practices, foster innovation, and improve the overall user experience for stakeholders.

Part B of the framework provides a curated list of methods and tools derived from relevant literature and existing OPERAS projects and services. A title, short description, usage guidance, components, key concepts, and additional sources for further exploration accompany each method. While this deliverable offers a limited overview of each method, an extended version will be developed within the OPERAS methods bank on the Confluence platform. Researchers are encouraged to familiarise themselves with the methods and have the flexibility to adapt them to their specific requirements. By leveraging this extensive collection of methods and tools, OPERAS project teams can enhance their UCD practices, ensuring the delivery of high-quality user experiences and driving advancements in open scholarly communication within the social sciences and humanities.

The UCQ-FRAME (version 1.0) will be iteratively revised to align with the project milestone MS6, which involves creating the first draft of the methodological framework for achieving user-centred quality objectives in OPERAS services. Stakeholder alignment meetings, executive presentations, feedback and input sessions, reporting and metrics, blog posts, and UCD workshops are examples of the following steps to be taken. This revision process will be completed by month 14 of the project, while the framework will also undergo experimentation with various services during the implementation phase in WP6 Task 6.3. These iterative processes ensure the ongoing relevance and practicality of the UCQ-FRAME throughout the project. By incorporating feedback and refining its

components, the UCQ-FRAME will provide valuable guidance and support for UCD practices, contributing to OPERAS' success in enhancing user engagement and delivering high-quality user experience.

Part B: Methods and tools for UCD

In contemporary UCD practice, various methods and tools facilitate effective communication, empathy, and engagement with users and stakeholders. UCD can be seen as a structured application of empathy, constantly expanding its toolkit with methods that gather diverse data to uncover users' thoughts, verbal expressions, and actions. Researchers and designers tackling this complex task need a well-rounded skill set and knowledge to select and apply the most appropriate methods for addressing specific questions. Although the provided list of methods and tools is incomplete, it will be regularly updated throughout the project and incorporated into the future OPERAS research methods bank. This compilation comprises prominent methods from academic and non-academic sources, organised alphabetically. Furthermore, an integrated table featuring a methods matrix aligns different methods with the UCD process, acknowledging the potential use of a single method across multiple phases (Table 6).

These are the five main phases of the UCD process:

1. **Planning** a UCD project - This phase includes defining and exploring project parts and defining the goal of the project.
2. **User research**: context of use and user requirements - This phase includes understanding user needs and requirements.
3. **Design solutions** - This phase includes participatory and generative design activities, and early prototyping of the first design.
4. **Evaluating the design** - This phase includes iterative testing and feedback to improve the design.
5. **Launching & monitoring** - This phase includes the system, product, or service launch after thorough design evaluation; opportunities to improve designs further and gather insights about the user experience through feedback; Continuous monitoring of usage analytics and better understanding of user behaviour.

Table 6: The methods matrix aligns different methods with the UCD process

Method	Planning	User research	Design solutions	Evaluating the design	Launching & monitoring
Affinity diagramming		●	●	●	●
Card sorting		●	●		
Cognitive walkthrough		●	●		
Competitive analysis	●				●
Content analysis		●	●	●	
Content inventory and audit	●				●
Contextual inquiry		●			
Critical Incident Technique	●	●			●
Cultural probes		●			
Diary Studies		●			
Empathy Maps		●			
Evaluative Research				●	
Eye Tracking				●	●
Focus Groups	●				●
Gap Analysis	●	●			
Heuristic Evaluation			●	●	
Interviews		●	●	●	
Key Performance Indicators					●

Observation		●			
Participatory Design		●	●	●	
Personas			●		
Prototyping			●	●	
Scenarios		●	●		
Service Design	●	●	●		
Shadowing	●			●	●
Stakeholder Walkthrough	●				
Storyboards			●		
Surveys			●		
Task Analysis		●			
Think-Aloud Protocol			●	●	
Tree Testing		●	●		
Usability Report			●	●	●
Usability Testing			●	●	●
User Journey Map			●		
Web Analytics					●
Wizard of Oz			●	●	

The list of selected user research methods and tools is organised in **alphabetical order**.

[A]

Affinity diagramming

Description: Affinity diagramming is a process used to externalise and meaningfully cluster observations and insights from research, or to organise some ideas about UX strategy and vision.

When to use it: after contextual inquiry interviews, or before usability testing, to prepare for each participant in different colours. The notes are grouped in a bottom-up approach.

What does it include: A board, sticky notes.

Key concepts describing affinity diagramming:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative	Observational
		Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- NN Group. Affinity Diagramming for Collaboratively Sorting UX Findings and Design Ideas. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/affinity-diagram/>
- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

[C]

Card sorting

Description: Card sorting is a method used for improving or designing information architecture.

When to use it: to learn how your users would use information. It can be used for qualitative or quantitative methodology: as an interview instrument or as a data collection tool.

What does it include: open (users write their own categories) and closed (usually used

for validations) card sorting, list of content topics and card for users - or conducting an online card sorting session.

Key concepts describing card sorting:

Behavioural	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational
		Evaluative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting
			Expert review
			Design process

Where to learn more:

- Rosenfeld Louis and Peter Morville. 2002. Information Architecture for the World Wide Web Louis Rosenfold and Peter Morville. 2nd ed.
- Usability.gov. Card sorting. <https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/card-sorting.html>

Cognitive walkthrough

Description: A cognitive walkthrough is a usability inspection method that evaluates a systems’ relative ease-of-use. The output of this method is a list of usability issues, sorted by severity ratings.

When to use it: to establish how easy a system is to use, and to identify usability problems on the interface.

What does it include: an evaluator (expert) who evaluates the interface from the perspective of the user; asks four questions:

- Will the user try and achieve the right outcome?
- Will the user notice that the correct action is available to them?
- Will the user associate the correct action with the outcome they expect to achieve?
- If the correct action is performed, will the user see that progress is being made towards their intended outcome?¹⁸

Key concepts describing cognitive walkthrough:

¹⁸ Interaction Design Foundation. How to Conduct a Cognitive Walkthrough. <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/how-to-conduct-a-cognitive-walkthrough>

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural Attitudinal	Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Exploratory Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory Observational Self reporting <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expert review Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Interaction Design Foundation. How to Conduct a Cognitive Walkthrough. <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/how-to-conduct-a-cognitive-walkthrough>
- NN Group. How to Conduct a Cognitive Walkthrough Workshop. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/cognitive-walkthrough-workshop/>
- Dix, A., Finlay, J., Abowd, G. D., & Beale, R. (2003). *Human-computer interaction*. Pearson Education.

[See also: Heuristic evaluation - Think aloud protocol - Wizard of Oz]

Competitive analysis

Description: Competitive analysis [similar to Competitive testing] is an examination and evaluation of competitor’s products and services, through various methods, such as heuristic evaluation or user feedback.

When to use it: in early design phases.

What does it include: competition product or sites, tested with or without users.

Key concepts describing competitive analysis:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural Attitudinal	Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Exploratory Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory Observational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting Expert review Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective*

solutions. Rockport.

- NN Group. Redesigning Your Website? Don't Ditch Your Old Design So Soon. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/redesign-competitive-testing/>

Content analysis

Description: Content analysis is a qualitative research method, a systematic description of form and content of written, spoken, or visual materials.

When to use it: to gain insights about the content of a website.

What does it include: Content analysis follows certain procedures: 1. Research questions formulated, 2. Sampling, 3. Forming units of analysis, 4. Creating coding categories, 5. Coding, 6. Analysis, 7. Interpretation

Key concepts describing content analysis:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

Content inventory & audit

Description: Content inventory is a list of the current digital content. It is usually organised in a spreadsheet. Content audit evaluates the quality of content listed in the content inventory.

When to use it: when beginning a website redesign, when merging multiple sites, splitting sites into smaller units, and when preparing content for multichannel distribution; to discover content that needs updating, gaps, and needs for removal of some content.

What does it include: inventory audits, evaluation criteria for the auditing process.

Key concepts describing content inventory and audit:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Exploratory Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory Observational Self reporting Expert review <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
- NN Group. Content Inventory and Auditing 101. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/content-audits/>

Contextual inquiry

Description: Contextual inquiry is a contextual research method of observing and interviewing; with the combination of observation and interview. Participants explain their actions or “think aloud” during the session, as they work through a task or activity. It is a structured, well-defined UCD process.

When to use it: In the discovery phase; to understand users in order to find out their fundamental intents, desires, and drivers. It is usually used to improve the ways in which people work; to understand communication flows, sequence of tasks, the artefacts and tools people use to accomplish work.

What does it include: 4 overall principles:

1. Context (interviews are conducted in a natural settings)
2. Partnership (user and researcher collaborate, participants talk about they work while they do the work, in order for the research data to be more reliable.
3. Interpretation (double-check of the data while on site, the researcher shares interpretation and insights with the user during the interview; the user may expand or correct the researcher’s understanding)
4. Focus (an opportunity for the researcher to refocus the interview for some participants, but to stay focused on the topics relevant to the scope).

Key concepts describing contextual inquiry:			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural Attitudinal	Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory Generative Evaluative	Participatory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting Expert review Design process
Where to learn more:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport. → Interaction Design Foundation Contextual Interviews and How to Handle Them. https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/contextual-interviews-and-how-to-handle-them 			
<p>[See also: Affinity diagramming - Interviews]</p>			

Critical Incident Technique			
<p>Description: Critical Incident Technique (CIT) is a research method in which the research participant is asked to retrospectively describe a situation about your product or a service. “Incidents” are captured through directed storytelling, interviews or diary studies. The goal is to generate representative scenarios that cover both positive and negative critical incidents, and include recommendations.</p> <p>When to use it: to define: the incident cause, user actions, user sentiment, incident outcome, ideal outcome.</p> <p>What does it include: 50-100 incidents are usually enough for a sample size. Positive and negative incidents are analysed and reported separately.</p> <p>Key concepts describing critical incident technique:</p>			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory Generative Evaluative	Participatory Observational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting Expert review <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
- NN Group. The Critical Incident Technique in UX. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/critical-incident-technique/>

Cultural probes

Description: Cultural probes represent a method that represents a tracking of users.

When to use it: In the exploration phase, to identify key patterns and themes that emerge from participants.

What does it include: Design probes gather information over a prolonged period, without the researcher, with a help of probe kits collected through personal stories, digital voice recorders, postcards, diaries, and stickers.

Key concepts describing cultural probes:

Behavioural

Quantitative

Exploratory

Participatory

Attitudinal

Qualitative

Generative

Observational

Evaluative

Self reporting

Expert review

Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

[D]

Diary Studies

Description: Diary Studies is a user research method used to collect qualitative data about long-term user behaviours and needs, such as habits, usage scenarios, attitudes and motivations, changes in behaviour and perceptions, and customer journeys. Data is collected longitudinally, over an extended period of time, by the user.

When to use it: to help define UX feature requirements, in an exploratory phase; to prepare the designer for further research by contributing to an understanding of participant user groups; to collect information from participants across time, sampling their thoughts, feelings and behaviours at key moments throughout a day, week, or month.

What does it include: digital diary; each page entry should be guided with a brief question or prompt, with appropriate space for encouraging the desired length of text.

Key concepts describing diary studies:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative Evaluative	Observational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting Expert review Design process

Where to learn more:

- NN Group: Diary Studies. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/diary-studies/>
- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

[E]

Empathy Maps

Description: Empathy map is an analysis technique, and synthesis. It is a visual tool designed to help gain a deeper understanding and compassion for customers, users, and stakeholders. It is a tool that helps empathise and synthesise observations from the research phase and draw unexpected insights about users' needs. It should be based on careful observations and analysis of how users behaved and responded to certain activities, suggestions, conversations etc.

When to use it: in the design phase. Similar to personas, the information collected to personas should be based on real research with actual people. They are a great background for the construction of the personas.

What does it include: *Four quadrants that refer to what the user: Said, Did, Thought, and Felt.*

Best practice for designing empathy maps:

1. Fill out the empathy map
2. Synthesise needs
3. Synthesise insights

Key concepts describing empathy maps:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative	Observational
		Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

Evaluative Research

Description: Evaluative research [Also called “user testing” or “product testing”] involves the testing of prototypes, products, or interfaces by real potential users of a system in design development. It is an iterative process, based on feedback from potential users.

When to use it: in an early-stage design, to inform new product development, to validate concepts, test prototypes, and find out if your project is on the right track.

What does it include: Formative (to test and evaluate solutions during the design process) and summative (at the end to evaluate the final solution) .

Key concepts describing evaluative research:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	Qualitative	Generative	Observational

		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting Expert review <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process
Where to learn more:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). <i>Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions</i>. Rockport. → User Research. Evaluative Research Methods. https://www.userinterviews.com/ux-research-field-guide-module/evaluative-methods 			

Eye Tracking			
<p>Description: Eye-tracking is a method used for measuring where users look on the page, where the eye is focused or the motion of the eye.</p> <p>When to use it: to gather detailed technical information on reading and scanning patterns during website navigation etc.</p> <p>What does it include: Eye tracking equipment.</p> <p>Key concepts describing eye tracking:</p>			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Qualitative	Exploratory Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational Self reporting Expert review Design process
Where to learn more:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Usability.gov. Eye Tracking. https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/eye-tracking.html → Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). <i>Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions</i>. Rockport. 			

[F]

Focus Groups

Description: Focus group is a qualitative UX research method that involves multiple users at the same time. In focus groups, a group of participants are asked their opinions, perceptions, beliefs, attitudes and practices regarding a product, service or concept. Focus groups are led by a skilled moderator (facilitator), who uses a script to ask questions. It is a recommendation that focus groups are supplemented with some quantitative and qualitative methods that continue to investigate attitudes and behaviours. Results from focus groups should never be extrapolated for how the population entirely feels (Hanington and Martin, 2019).

When to use it: to discover what users want from the system.

What does it include: 6-9 users, a moderator.

Key concepts describing focus groups:

Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative	Observational
		Evaluative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting
			Expert review
			Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.
- NN Group. The Use and Misuse of Focus Groups. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/focus-groups/>

[G]

Gap Analysis

Description: an approach aimed at identifying current (problems) and preferred or desired goals.

When to use it: in the first phases of design, to produce usability objectives, and informing the design process, and gaining insights about the areas that

need improvements.

What does it include: evaluating the current state of user experience, identification of gaps, prioritising results (usually with sticky notes), developing a plan for the improvement.

Key concepts describing gap analysis:

Behavioural Attitudinal	Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory Generative Evaluative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Participatory Observational Self reporting Expert review Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

[H]

Heuristic evaluation

Description: Heuristic evaluation is an informal usability inspection method in which evaluators assess an interface against a set of heuristics.

When to use it: early in the design process, to evaluate the usability and effectiveness of a system.

What does it include: Experts, evaluators, a set of heuristics (such as Jakob Nielsen’s 10 usability heuristics, “rules of thumb”).

Key concepts describing heuristic evaluation:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Exploratory Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory Observational Self reporting <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expert review Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
- NN Group. 10 Usability Heuristics for User Interface Design. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ten-usability-heuristics/>

Interviews

Description: An interview is a social science research method employed in UX research. Conducting user interviews provides learning about users' perceptions of your design, not about usability. Questions are usually about some topic of interest, such as use of a system, behaviours and habits, feelings, motivations e.g. Whether people would use your design, although design (early sketch, prototype or working software) is not necessary for this method (vs. usability test where users interact with the design).

When to use it: [User interviews](#) are typically performed with the potential users of design, as a part of an ideation phase or during early concept development.

Interviews give insights about what a user thinks about a site, an application, a product, or a process. Interviews can be conducted:

- Before you have a design, to inform personas, journey maps, ideas, workflow ideas
- To enrich a contextual inquiry (a study by supplementing observation with description of tools, processes, bottlenecks, and how users perceive them)
- At the end of usability test, to collect verbal responses related to observed behaviours

What does it include: Script for guiding the interview, software for later data analysis.

Key concepts describing interviews:

Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting
			Expert review
			Design process

Where to learn more:

- Nielsen Norman Group: <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/user-interviews/>
- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.
- <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/user-intervi>

[K]

Key Performance Indicators

Description: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are measurements of how well you are doing against business goals. In UX, they are used to measure the effectiveness of a product or a website in meeting user needs and goals.

By regularly monitoring and analysing KPIs, UX designers can improve the overall usability and effectiveness of a product or a website.

When to use it: at the beginning of the initiative.

What does it include: metrics such as user satisfaction, task completion rate, bounce rate.

Key concepts describing key performance indicators:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
Attitudinal	Qualitative	Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.
- UX Planet. Important UX KPIs and how to measure them. <https://uxplanet.org/important-ux-kpis-and-how-to-measure-them-cdbddd610870>

[O]

Observation

Description: User observation is a technique that focuses on what the users actually do as opposed to what they say they do. The two most common techniques used for observing users are:

- Controlled observations: conducted in laboratory environments.
- Naturalistic observations: observing user behaviour with the product as they use it in day-to-day life.
- [Netnography](#): engage in the observation of various online communities and their behaviours; mainly focus on studying sensitive topics by conveniently accessing online information anonymously.

When to use it: In order to understand the usability of a product and to some extent the overall user experience; in the ideation phase, in order to generate lots of ideas for the improvement of the product or a service.

What does it include:

Key concepts describing observation:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational
		Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			Design process

Where to learn more:

- Interaction Design Foundation. <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/how-to-conduct-user-observations>
- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

[P]

Participatory Design

Description: Participatory design is a human-centred approach that involves users and stakeholders in the design process, ideally in activity-based co-design engagements.

When to use it: in the beginning of the design process, in ideation phases.

What does it include: Different methods such as workshops, cultural probes, diary studies, photo studies, collage etc.

Key concepts describing participatory design:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
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Personas

Description: User personas is a technique for prototyping, analysis technique and research deliverable technique. User personas are descriptions or representations of a typical user group of a product or a service which is developed. Personas don't describe real people. Persona is a representation of a typical group with the same patterns, such as behaviour, needs, goals, skills, and attitudes. They are a quick and easy way to present user goals and characteristics. It should be based on real research with actual people.

When to use it: to prioritise design, to understand user needs, and to decide what functionalities to include in the design.

What does it include: Personas usually include:

Set of goals related to the system or service under development.

Descriptions of skills, attitudes, tasks, motivations, frustrations, and environment.

Key concepts describing affinity personas:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative	Observational
		Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
- Cooper, Alan, Robert Reimann, David Cronin, and Christopher Noessel. 2014. About Face: The Essentials of Interaction Design. John Wiley & Sons.

Prototyping

Description: Prototyping is a visual representation of different levels of design process, in the form of sketches, or more precise design solutions.

When to use it: to test early iteratively through the design process.

What does it include: prototypes can be low-fidelity, such as scenarios, storyboards, and wireframes, or high-fidelity prototypes, which are more defined.

Key concepts describing affinity prototyping:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

[S]

Scenarios

Description: Scenario is a narrative that explains and usually represents a (future) use of a product or a service by the user. Differentiating between "as-is" and "to-be" scenarios involve recognising the contrast between the current narrative description of a specific user's procedure (as-is scenario) and the projected or envisioned narrative description of their future procedure (to-be scenario) to complete tasks. Personas, scenarios, and storyboards work well together.

When to use it: in exploration phase to identify user needs, and in early prototyping phase, to make design ideas more concrete and understandable.

What does it include: Scenarios are written in a form of story with few visuals, and it is recommended that scenarios are written from the personas point of view.

Key concepts describing affinity scenarios:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative	Observational
		Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
- Cooper, Alan, Robert Reimann, David Cronin, and Christopher Noessel. 2014. About Face: The Essentials of Interaction Design. John Wiley & Sons.

Service Design

Description: Service Design is an approach for understanding, organising and planning business resources (people, products and processes) in order to improve the user experience.

When to use it: in early phases of planning, exploration and prototyping.

What does it include: People (anyone who creates or uses the service), Props (every component needed to perform the service), Processes (workflows, procedures performed by the employees or the users). A visual representation of Service design is called a service blueprint. It is a diagram visualising the relationship between different service components. It is usually seen as a part two to creating customer journey maps.

Key concepts describing service design:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory Observational Self reporting Expert review <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
- NN Group. Service Design: Study Guide.
<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/service-design-study-guide/>

Shadowing

Description: Shadowing is a research technique widely implemented in user research; which provides key insights into a participant’s activities and decision patterns as the researcher follows the participant closely throughout daily routines. Several team members complete shadowing exercises across representative users, to begin. The researchers act as observers only.

When to use it: in early design phase.

What does it include: the researcher, the user, and the observer.

Key concepts describing shadowing:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural Attitudinal	Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory Generative Evaluative	Participatory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational Self reporting Expert review Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.
- Interaction Design Foundation. Shadowing in User Research - Do You See What They See? <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/shadowing-in-user-research-do-you-see-what-they-see>

Stakeholder walkthrough

Description: Stakeholder Walkthrough is a research method in which end users, stakeholders and the design team evaluate early prototypes and task-based scenarios from the end users perspective, providing actionable recommendations for improvements.

When to use it: in prototyping phase.

What does it include: representative users, stakeholders, developers, and members of the design and research team. Stakeholder maps are useful to visually consolidate and communicate the key constituents of a design project, setting the stage for user-centred research and design development.

Key concepts describing stakeholder walkthrough:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

Storyboards

Description: Storyboard is a technique for prototyping and research deliverable. Storyboards provide a visual narrative that generates empathy and communicates the context in which a technology or form factor will be used. The storyboard is a Lo-Fi illustration in a row that represents a sequence and tells a story. The storyboard illustrates how users could use a particular system in real life. It describes the user's activities and represents potential design.

When to use it: At the beginning of a product or system development.

What does it include: Different scenarios and stories around the product to give the viewer an impression of the system. It is not about detailed screens or functions, it is about a concept as a whole.

Key concepts describing storyboards:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative	Observational
		Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems, develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

Surveys

Description: Survey is a research method used to primarily collect quantitative data about users' interactions and experiences with a website or digital product. However, qualitative items are also often included in the survey questionnaires.

When to use it: The main purpose of using a survey is to collect reliable data from a representative sample of users in order to measure the level of usability or user experience with a product or service. Those measures are usually subjective and give insights into the perceived usability and user experience qualities of a service or a system.

What does it include: different tools for online surveys, combining different types of survey questions. Psychometrically validated scales are often included in surveys. For

example, SUS and UEQ.

Key concepts describing surveys:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative Evaluative	Observational
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting
			Expert review
			Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

[T]

Task analysis

Description: Task Analysis is a research method that shows how users complete their tasks and achieve their goals. A task refers to any activity that is observable, and has a start and end point.

When to use it: In the exploration phase, to learn how users work (perform tasks), in order to achieve their goals.

What does it include: 1. Gather information on goals and tasks (by observing and speaking to users and/or subject matter experts), 2. Analyse the tasks performed to achieve their goals (to understand the overall number of tasks, subtasks, their sequence, hierarchy and complexity; usually documented in diagrams).

Key concepts describing task:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exploratory	Participatory
Attitudinal	Qualitative	Generative Evaluative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observational
			Self reporting
			Expert review
			Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to*

research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

Think-aloud Protocol

Description: Think-aloud protocol is a method in which participants verbalise what they are doing while completing some task.

When to use it: in the prototyping and evaluating phase.

What does it include: Concurrent think-aloud (the participant works through the task while articulating what he is doing; the focus is on *what* is happening, instead of *why*); Retrospective think-aloud (participant finishes a task in silence, and upon task completion; participant retrospectively comments and watch the replay of their recorded performed task).

Key concepts describing think-aloud protocol:

Behavioural

Attitudinal

Quantitative

Qualitative

Exploratory

Generative

Evaluative

Participatory

Observational

Self reporting

Expert review

Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.
- NN Group: Task Analysis: Support Users in Achieving Their Goals <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/task-analysis/>

Tree testing

Description: Tree testing is an evaluative method used in information architecture, to measure how easily people find content on the website/application, and to improve the information architecture of the website.

When to use it: In exploration and prototype phase.

What does it include: Study design, tree testing tools.

Key concepts describing tree testing:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative Qualitative	Exploratory Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory Observational <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Self reporting Expert review Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

[U]

Usability Report

 Description: Usability report is a research deliverable, informed by empirical evidence. It is crucial for projects, to archive it for future needs, revisions, or further testing.

When to use it: in prototyping, evaluation, and testing phase.

What does it include: Interactive repositories that includes the following: executive summary, total number of problems found, the list of problems that need to be fixed, reports on positive findings, detailed tasks and scenario descriptions.

Key concepts describing usability report:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Exploratory Generative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Participatory Observational Self reporting Expert review <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process
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Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective

solutions. Rockport.

Usability testing

Description: Usability testing is an evaluative research method in which a researcher observes interaction of the user and digital product, while the user walks through a set of predefined tasks.

When to use it: in prototyping, evaluation and testing phase.

What does it include: Usability tests are designed around different tasks and scenarios that represent typical end-user goals, that have to be specific, concrete and represent actual goals of the target audience.

Key concepts describing usability testing:

Behavioural

Attitudinal

Quantitative

Qualitative

Exploratory

Generative

Evaluative

Participatory

Observational

Self reporting

Expert review

Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions. Rockport.

User journey map

Description: User journey map (also: Customer journey map), a research deliverable is a visual tool that illustrates user flow during the interaction with a product or a service.

When to use it: User journey maps are usually created alongside or immediately following personas and scenario documents. All three deliverables should be informed with direct contact with the customers who use the product or service.

What does it include: User journey map should represent a journey specific to a persona and include a description of the persona. It should also show an event it

illustrates: an entire relationship lifecycle or can be limited to a specific scenario.

Key concepts describing user journey maps:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Attitudinal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Qualitative	Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

[W]

Web Analytics

Description: Web analytics are measurements of a user behaviour, conducted to find out what users are doing on your website or application.

When to use it: In test and implementation phase.

What does it include: definition of what kind of data to measure, collect data, analyse data in reports. It is possible to combine web analytics with methods such as A/B testing, Search Site Analytic, Eye Tracking, Usability Testing.

Key concepts describing web analytics:

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Behavioural	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Quantitative	Exploratory	Participatory
Attitudinal	Qualitative	Generative	Observational
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Evaluative	Self reporting
			Expert review
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.

Wizard of Oz

Description: Wizard of Oz is a moderated user-research method in which a researcher (the “wizard”) simulates interaction with an interface.

When to use it: In prototyping and evaluation phase, before investing time and money in the actual prototype.

What does it include: a wizard (researcher), and a variation of prototype.

Key concepts describing Wizard of Oz:

Behavioural

Attitudinal

Quantitative

Qualitative

Exploratory

Generative

Evaluative

Participatory

Observational

Self reporting

Expert review

Design process

Where to learn more:

- Hanington B. & Martin B. (2019). *Universal methods of design : 125 ways to research complex problems develop innovative ideas and design effective solutions*. Rockport.
- NN Group. The Wizard of Oz Method in UX.
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